

Shift, Symmetry, and Asymmetry in Polynomial Sequences.

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Abstract.

In this study, we show the existence of three types of shifts in polynomial curves in the XY-plane that will always result in integer sequences: 1. "Eureka shift", 2. Taylor shift, and 3. "Taylor shift and fit". Offset is a particular case of integer Taylor shift values. From these polynomial shift properties, we prove that there is always an absolute offset position provided by the simplest polynomial equation of all. We define mathematically what is the simplest polynomial equation of all. When we use this simplest equation of all, we can assign to any polynomial sequence an absolute value to offset $f = 0$. In the current literature, we have three staircase functions[19] with unit steps: 1. floor, 2. ceiling, and 3. round. We show that there is no current staircase function with a unit step to express exactly the result of the offset in the polynomial integer sequences. To properly portray the offset of polynomial integer sequences, it is necessary to create a new fourth staircase function with a unit step. Just as the floor function has a complementary function ceiling, we realized that we need to create a complementary round staircase function. We call this new mathematical staircase function "round half to zero" and abbreviate it as "roundz". This new function "roundz" rounds the half value to 0 instead of 1. It can portray exactly what happens to the symmetry point when we implement offset in a polynomial sequence of integers. Then, we prove that every polynomial equation has a reference point that we call the "symmetry point" (sp). The symmetry point is always found between the elements with the smallest values (or the highest, if changing the signal) in the polynomial sequence. From the symmetry point of any polynomial sequence of integers, we can define two types of symmetry and one type of asymmetry. We name and define the sequences asymmetry and the two types of symmetries. With the definitions of symmetry, we show that we can make some similar relationships between the properties of polynomial infinite sequences and the finite sequences of divisors of integers.

Keywords.

Polynomial Integer Sequences; Recurrence; Symmetry; Asymmetry; Taylor Series.

2020 Mathematics Subject Classification.

11Y55; 97I30; 65N06; 65Q30; 41A58.

1. Introduction.

Let the initial polynomial $x = Yd[y] = a_d y^d + a_{d-1} y^{d-1} + a_{d-2} y^{d-2} + \dots + a_4 y^4 + a_3 y^3 + a_2 y^2 + b y + c$, where the index y , the degree d , and the coefficients a_n result in an integer sequence. Note that we can have non-integer coefficients and still obtain a sequence of integers. This occurs with an infinite number of polynomials such as <https://oeis.org/A000217>.

When we draw this function $x = Yd[y]$ in the XY plane, we obtain the polynomial curve.

We can move the polynomial curve just along the X-axis (item 2), just along the Y-axis (item 3), or both in any combination (item 4). There is no rotation of the curve when we do a shift. The curve shift is always continuous.

When the polynomial curve $x = Y[y]$ moves only in the direction of the y-index in unit steps, we always produce a different offset for the same sequence of integers (item 5).

At the same time, the Taylor shift shows that the coefficient of the highest degree never changes when we change the offset of a polynomial sequence, but all other coefficients necessarily change.

In other words, when we vary the sequence offset, we vary all the coefficients of the polynomial except the coefficient with the highest degree. Consequently, in one offset direction the variable coefficients increase in absolute value and in the other offset direction the variable coefficients decrease in absolute value.

Additionally, no matter how much we decrease the absolute values of the variable coefficients, the Taylor shift shows us that at some point these absolute values of the variable coefficients will increase again. This occurs for any polynomial.

Therefore, every polynomial sequence has an offset that has an equation with the smallest absolute values of the coefficients. Therefore, all polynomial sequences have an increasing or decreasing direction of offset variation where the corresponding decreasing or increasing variation of the a_{d-1} coefficient of the second highest degree of the polynomial will occur.

Whatever the polynomial sequence, there will always be a certain offset that produces the smallest absolute value of the a_{d-1} coefficient of the second highest degree of the polynomial.

At this offset value, the polynomial sequence assumes "the simplest polynomial equation of all"(item 6).

So, we conclude that for each polynomial sequence we can set an offset of value $f = 0$ which is "the simplest polynomial equation of all"(item 7, 8 and 9).

When we discover that all polynomial sequences have an absolute offset $f = 0$ and it is not randomly chosen by us, then we begin to realize that in all polynomial curves there is a region that generates elements with "small" finite absolute values and that are the smallest of all other elements up to infinity.

This suggests that there is a reference point in this region of the lowest finite absolute values. If such a reference point exists, then it "sees" all infinitely many points equally in the sequence at any offset. And for this reference point to also see all the infinite points and elements of the polynomial curve as "equally" or "symmetrically" as possible, then this reference point has to be a symmetry point that is "equidistant from the two infinities" which any polynomial sequence has. Therefore, in item 10 we defined the "symmetry point" for any polynomial.

In item 11 we show the application of Taylor shift to transform any polynomial equation up to 5th degree into an offset $f = 0$, as well as the pair of coordinates (x_{sp}, y_{sp}) of the symmetry point.

Because we have proven the existence of a symmetry point in any polynomial sequence, so in section 13 we make a reasoning of how the existence of a symmetry point can "see" in any sequence of integers, not only restricted to polynomials.

In this reasoning, we conclude that there are two types of integer sequence symmetries, SUB and DES, and only one type of asymmetry, ACC.

Next, in item 15 we show how the bijection function (one-to-one correspondence) can conclusively define the symmetry or asymmetry of any sequence of integers.

Then in item 16 we make a formal mathematical definition of each of the two polynomial symmetries and the asymmetry. Now we show how the symmetry point is positioned according to the symmetry of the polynomial sequence at offset $f = 0$.

In section 17 we define the three types of lines of symmetry that exist in the curves of polynomial sequences of integers.

To show how the idea of two types of symmetries in sequences of integers expands into areas other than polynomials, we use some concepts from the studies of sequences of divisors of integers to apply to polynomials. These same concepts of symmetry can be applied to Midy's theorem.

This equivalence of symmetry between polynomial sequences, with the symmetries of the sequences of the divisors of the integers and others such as the symmetries of the repetend of the inverses of the integers (Midy's theorem), allows us to exchange properties and applications between them. To do this, we have included the examples in items 18 and 19.

At the end we show an example of the geometry of how the symmetry point of an asymmetric quadratic sequence "sees" all the infinite elements. We suggest adding a unique and universal way to classify the polynomial sequences of integers. The classification is always a finite sequence of elements that form the polynomial equation of offset $f = 0$. It is a finite sequence that generates the infinite polynomial sequence. This avoids duplicate classification of the same number sequence.

We end the study by making a symmetry summary for the quadratics and another for any polynomial.

2. The “Eureka shift”.

If we shift the initial polynomial curve $Y[y] = a_d y^d + a_{d-1} y^{d-1} + a_{d-2} y^{d-2} + \dots + a_4 y^4 + a_3 y^3 + a_2 y^2 + a_1 y + c$ along the X-axis, we obtain:

$$Y^o[y] = Y[y] + m$$

$$Y^o[y] = a_d y^d + a_{d-1} y^{d-1} + a_{d-2} y^{d-2} + \dots + a_4 y^4 + a_3 y^3 + a_2 y^2 + a_1 y + c + m$$

Now, $c^o = c + m$, and:

$$Y^o[y] = a_d y^d + a_{d-1} y^{d-1} + a_{d-2} y^{d-2} + \dots + a_4 y^4 + a_3 y^3 + a_2 y^2 + a_1 y + c^o$$

Let us define "Eureka shift" as the shifts along the X-axis to $m = \text{integer}$. In this way, for any Eureka shift, we will always obtain a new sequence of integers.

In the eureka shift we only change the constant c to produce a new integer sequence.

We propose to call "Eureka Shift" inspired by Neil Sloane video available online at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6X2D497is6Y0> and Eureka sequences at <https://www.curiousstem.org/stem-articles/eureka-sequences>. In this way, we can obtain a kind of "Eureka" polynomial sequence.

3. The Taylor shift.

If we shift the initial polynomial curve $Y[y] = a_d y^d + a_{d-1} y^{d-1} + a_{d-2} y^{d-2} + \dots + a_4 y^4 + a_3 y^3 + a_2 y^2 + a_1 y + c$ along the Y-axis, we obtain:

$$Y[y + h] = a_d (y + h)^d + a_{d-1} (y + h)^{d-1} + a_{d-2} (y + h)^{d-2} + \dots + a_4 (y + h)^4 + a_3 (y + h)^3 + a_2 (y + h)^2 + a_1 (y + h) + c$$

We can analyze this Y-axis shift $h = \text{Real}$ using the Taylor expansion at $y = h$.

$$Y[y] = \sum_{n=0}^d \frac{Y^{[n]}[h]}{n!} (y - h)^n$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Y[y] &= Y[h] + Y^{[1]}[h](y-h) + \frac{Y^{[2]}[h]}{2!}(y-h)^2 + \frac{Y^{[3]}[h]}{3!}(y-h)^3 + \dots \\
&\quad + \frac{Y^{[d-3]}[h]}{(d-3)!}(y-h)^{(d-3)} + \frac{Y^{[d-2]}[h]}{(d-2)!}(y-h)^{(d-2)} + \frac{Y^{[d-1]}[h]}{(d-1)!}(y-h)^{(d-1)} \\
&\quad + \frac{Y^{[d]}[h]}{d!}(y-h)^d
\end{aligned}$$

Let us write the polynomial above reversing the direction of its terms:

$$\begin{aligned}
Y[y] &= \frac{Y^{[d]}[h]}{d!}(y-h)^d + \frac{Y^{[d-1]}[h]}{(d-1)!}(y-h)^{(d-1)} + \frac{Y^{[d-2]}[h]}{(d-2)!}(y-h)^{(d-2)} \\
&\quad + \frac{Y^{[d-3]}[h]}{(d-3)!}(y-h)^{(d-3)} + \dots + \frac{Y^{[3]}[h]}{3!}(y-h)^3 + \frac{Y^{[2]}[h]}{2!}(y-h)^2 \\
&\quad + Y^{[1]}[h](y-h) + Y[h]
\end{aligned}$$

So,

$$\begin{aligned}
Y[y+h] &= \frac{Y^{[d]}[h]}{d!}y^d + \frac{Y^{[d-1]}[h]}{(d-1)!}y^{(d-1)} + \frac{Y^{[d-2]}[h]}{(d-2)!}y^{(d-2)} + \frac{Y^{[d-3]}[h]}{(d-3)!}y^{(d-3)} + \dots \\
&\quad + \frac{Y^{[3]}[h]}{3!}y^3 + \frac{Y^{[2]}[h]}{2!}y^2 + Y^{[1]}[h]y + Y[h]
\end{aligned}$$

Let us say,

$$Y[y+h] = a_d^{\circ}y^d + a_{d-1}^{\circ}y^{d-1} + a_{d-2}^{\circ}y^{d-2} + \dots + a_3^{\circ}y^3 + a_2^{\circ}y^2 + b^{\circ}y + c^{\circ}$$

Or,

$$Y[y+h] = a_d^{\circ}y^d + a_{d-1}^{\circ}y^{d-1} + a_{d-2}^{\circ}y^{d-2} + \dots + a_3^{\circ}y^3 + a_2^{\circ}y^2 + a_1^{\circ}y + a_0^{\circ}$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
a_d^{\circ} &= \frac{Y^{[d]}[h]}{d!} \\
a_{d-1}^{\circ} &= \frac{Y^{[d-1]}[h]}{(d-1)!} \\
a_{d-2}^{\circ} &= \frac{Y^{[d-2]}[h]}{(d-2)!} \\
&\dots \\
a_2^{\circ} &= a^{\circ} = \frac{Y^{[2]}[h]}{2!} \\
a_1^{\circ} &= b^{\circ} = Y^{[1]}[h] \\
a_0^{\circ} &= c^{\circ} = Y[h]
\end{aligned}$$

Because,

$$Y[y] = a_d y^d + a_{d-1} y^{d-1} + a_{d-2} y^{d-2} + \dots + a_3 y^3 + a_2 y^2 + a_1 y + a_0$$

Then,

$$a_0^{\circ} = Y[h] = a_d h^d + a_{d-1} h^{d-1} + a_{d-2} h^{d-2} + \dots + a_3 h^3 + a_2 h^2 + a_1 h + a_0$$

$$a_1^{\circ} = Y^{[1]}[h] = d a_d h^{d-1} + (d-1) a_{d-1} h^{d-2} + (d-2) a_{d-2} h^{d-3} + \dots + 3 a_3 h^2 + 2 a_2 h + a_1$$

$$a_2^{\circ} = \frac{Y^{[2]}[h]}{2!} = \frac{d(d-1) a_d h^{d-2} + (d-1)(d-2) a_{d-1} h^{d-3} + \dots + 3 \cdot 2 \cdot a_3 h + 2 a_2}{2!}$$

...

$$\begin{aligned} a_{d-3}^{\circ} &= \frac{Y^{[d-3]}[h]}{(d-3)!} \\ &= \left(\frac{d(d-1)(d-2)}{3!} a_d h^3 + \frac{(d-1)(d-2)}{2} a_{d-1} h^2 + (d-2) a_{d-2} h \right) \\ &\quad + \frac{(d-3)! a_{d-3}}{(d-3)!} \\ &= \frac{d(d-1)(d-2)}{3!} a_d h^3 + \frac{(d-1)(d-2)}{2} a_{d-1} h^2 + (d-2) a_{d-2} h + a_{d-3} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} a_{d-2}^{\circ} &= \frac{Y^{[d-2]}[h]}{(d-2)!} = \frac{\left(\frac{d! a_d h}{2} + (d-1)! a_{d-1} \right) h + (d-2)! a_{d-2}}{(d-2)!} \\ &= \frac{d(d-1)}{2} a_d h^2 + (d-1) a_{d-1} h + a_{d-2} \end{aligned}$$

$$a_{d-1}^{\circ} = \frac{Y^{[d-1]}[h]}{(d-1)!} = \frac{d! a_d h + (d-1)! a_{d-1}}{(d-1)!} = d a_d h + a_{d-1}$$

$$a_d^{\circ} = \frac{Y^{[d]}[h]}{d!} = \frac{d! a_d}{d!} = a_d$$

Because in the Taylor shift, we change the index value of the polynomial, we change all the coefficients in the polynomial equation except the coefficient of the highest degree.

4. “Taylor shift and fit”.

Because of this alteration of all coefficients but one, to produce a new sequence of integers, we may also consider the Taylor shift of noninteger real values of the polynomial curves.

For example, let us do a shift from the square numbers curve to the oblong numbers curve.

The sequence <https://oeis.org/A000290> square numbers is the polynomial $Y[y] = y^2$.

When we apply a Taylor shift of $h = -\frac{1}{2}$, we obtain the polynomial curve $Y^{\circ}[y] = Y\left[y - \frac{1}{2}\right] = y^2 - y + \frac{1}{4}$.

First notice that by making a Taylor shift to a negative value, the polynomial curve shifts in the positive direction of the Y-axis.

Now, shifting the curve just along the X-axis in its opposite direction by an amount of $\frac{1}{4}$ results in the polynomial curve $Y[y] = y^2 - y$, which is the oblong sequence <https://oeis.org/A002378>.

This fractional shift along the X-axis compensates for the noninteger Taylor shift to produce a new sequence of integers.

This noninteger “Taylor shift compensation” is the equivalent of using the floor function on all elements in the resulting sequence. In our example:

$$\text{oblong sequence} = \left\lfloor y^2 - y + \frac{1}{4} \right\rfloor = y^2 - y$$

In the Cartesian plane, it is similar to applying the noninteger Taylor shift to a curve and fitting it back to the cross-integer XY coordinates again.

Let us give the name “Taylor shift and fit” to every noninteger Taylor shift applied to a polynomial curve that needs X-axis direction shift compensation to generate a new sequence of integers.

5. Offset in polynomials.

We define the offset in a polynomial $Y[y]$ as the Taylor shift $Y^{\circ}[y] = Y[y + h]$ if and only if $h = -f = \text{integer}$.

We use the letter f to denote the offset. Always offset $f = \text{integer}$.

6. The simplest polynomial equation.

Let us prove that any quadratic sequence has the simplest equation of all. By induction, we can extend the same reasoning to any polynomial sequence.

When we say that 3 sequential elements $\{x_1, x_2, x_3\} = \{Y[y_1], Y[y_2], Y[y_3]\}$ define completely a quadratic sequence, we mean that each element is the $x_n = Y[y_n]$ result of the quadratic equation $x = Y[y] = ay^2 + by + c$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 &= Y[y_1] = ay_1^2 + by_1 + c \\ x_2 &= Y[y_2] = ay_2^2 + by_2 + c \\ x_3 &= Y[y_3] = ay_3^2 + by_3 + c \end{aligned}$$

In one direction, we have the standard $y_3 = y_2 + 1 = y_1 + 2$.

In the reversal order, $y_3 = y_2 - 1 = y_1 - 2$.

So,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \dots \\
 & \text{for } y = 3, \text{ then } Y[3] = 9a + 3b + c \\
 & \text{for } y = 2, \text{ then } Y[2] = 4a + 2b + c \\
 & \text{for } y = 1, \text{ then } Y[1] = a + b + c \\
 & \text{for } y = 0, \text{ then } Y[0] = c \\
 & \text{for } y = -1, \text{ then } Y[-1] = a - b + c \\
 & \text{for } y = -2, \text{ then } Y[-2] = 4a - 2b + c \\
 & \text{for } y = -3, \text{ then } Y[-3] = 9a - 3b + c \\
 & \dots
 \end{aligned}$$

Is there a setting that is simpler than all the others?

6.1. Set 1 of 5:

If we look at Robert Sacks' www.NumberSpiral.com study, we will conclude that he used this choice set 1 of 5:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{for } y_3 = 3, \text{ then } k = Y[3] = 9a + 3b + c \\
 & \text{for } y_2 = 2, \text{ then } j = Y[2] = 4a + 2b + c \\
 & \text{for } y_1 = 1, \text{ then } i = Y[1] = a + b + c
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, when NumberSpiral created 3 simultaneous equations for elements named (i, j, k) , they set $y_1 = 1$. He wrote: “the first number, $Y[1] = i$, is generated when we plug $y = 1$ into $Y[y] = ay^2 + by + c$ expression. The next number, $Y[2] = j$, since it is the very next number in the sequence after $Y[1] = i$, is generated by $y = 2$. Similarly, $Y[3] = k$ is generated by $y = 3$ ”.

Then, the result obtained is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 a &= \frac{i - 2j + k}{2} = \frac{Y[1] - 2Y[2] + Y[3]}{2} \\
 b &= j - i - 3a = Y[2] - Y[1] - 3a \\
 c &= i - a - b = Y[1] - a - b
 \end{aligned}$$

or,

$$\begin{aligned}
 a &= \frac{i - 2j + k}{2} = \frac{Y[1] - 2Y[2] + Y[3]}{2} \\
 b &= \frac{-5i + 8j - 3k}{2} = \frac{-5Y[1] + 8Y[2] - 3Y[3]}{2} \\
 c &= 3i - 3j + k = 3Y[1] - 3Y[2] + Y[3]
 \end{aligned}$$

where the final expression of the quadratic is:

$$Y[y] = \left(\frac{i-2j+k}{2}\right)y^2 + \left(\frac{-5i+8j-3k}{2}\right)y + (3i-3j+k)$$

or,

$$Y_{Set\ 1\ of\ 5}[y] = \left(\frac{Y[1]-2Y[2]+Y[3]}{2}\right)y^2 + \left(\frac{-5Y[1]+8Y[2]-3Y[3]}{2}\right)y + (3Y[1]-3Y[2]+Y[3])$$

[NumberSpiral](#) used $y_1 = 1$, $y_2 = 2$, and $y_3 = 3$. If we set $y_1 = 2$, $y_2 = 3$, and $y_3 = 4$, we obtain the same coefficient $a = \frac{i-2j+k}{2} = \frac{Y[1]-2Y[2]+Y[3]}{2}$ but more complex terms for coefficients b and c.

Therefore, let us continue in the opposite direction and analyze set 2 of 5, where $y_1 = 0$, $y_2 = 1$, and $y_3 = 2$.

6.2. Set 2 of 5:

Considering,

$$\text{for } y_3 = 2, \text{ then } Y[2] = 4a + 2b + c$$

$$\text{for } y_2 = 1, \text{ then } Y[1] = a + b + c$$

$$\text{for } y_1 = 0, \text{ then } Y[0] = c$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned} c &= Y[0] \\ Y[1] &= a + b + Y[0] \\ Y[2] &= 4a + 2b + Y[0] \end{aligned}$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned} 2Y[1] &= 2a + 2b + 2Y[0] \\ Y[2] - 2Y[1] &= 4a + 2b + Y[0] - 2a - 2b - 2Y[0] \\ Y[2] - 2Y[1] &= 2a - Y[0] \\ a &= \frac{Y[0] - 2Y[1] + Y[2]}{2} \end{aligned}$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned} Y[1] &= a + b + Y[0] \\ Y[1] &= \frac{Y[0] - 2Y[1] + Y[2]}{2} + b + Y[0] \\ 2Y[1] &= Y[0] - 2Y[1] + Y[2] + 2b + 2Y[0] \\ 4Y[1] &= 3Y[0] + Y[2] + 2b \\ b &= \frac{-3Y[0] + 4Y[1] - Y[2]}{2} \end{aligned}$$

Finally,

$$Y_{Set\ 2\ of\ 5}[y] = \left(\frac{Y[0]-2Y[1]+Y[2]}{2}\right)y^2 + \left(\frac{-3Y[0]+4Y[1]-Y[2]}{2}\right)y + Y[0]$$

6.3. Set 3 of 5:

Considering,

$$\text{for } y_3 = 1, \text{ then } Y[1] = a + b + c$$

$$\text{for } y_2 = 0, \text{ then } Y[0] = c$$

$$\text{for } y_1 = -1, \text{ then } Y[-1] = a - b + c$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned}c &= Y[0] \\ Y[-1] &= a - b + Y[0] \\ Y[1] &= a + b + Y[0]\end{aligned}$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned}Y[-1] + Y[1] &= 2a + Y[0] \\ a &= \frac{Y[-1] - 2Y[0] + Y[1]}{2}\end{aligned}$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned}Y[1] - Y[-1] &= 2b \\ b &= \frac{Y[1] - Y[-1]}{2}\end{aligned}$$

Finally,

$$Y_{Set\ 3\ of\ 5}[y] = \left(\frac{Y[-1]-2Y[0]+Y[1]}{2}\right)y^2 + \left(\frac{Y[1]-Y[-1]}{2}\right)y + Y[0]$$

6.4. Set 4 of 5:

Considering,

$$\text{for } y_3 = 0, \text{ then } Y[0] = c$$

$$\text{for } y_2 = -1, \text{ then } Y[-1] = a - b + c$$

$$\text{for } y_1 = -2, \text{ then } Y[-2] = 4a - 2b + c$$

Then,

$$c = Y[0]$$

$$Y[-2] = 4a - 2b + Y[0]$$

$$Y[-1] = a - b + Y[0]$$

Then,

$$Y[-2] - 2Y[-1] = 4a - 2b + Y[0] - 2a + 2b - 2Y[0]$$

$$Y[-2] - 2Y[-1] = 2a - Y[0]$$

$$a = \frac{Y[-2] - 2Y[-1] + Y[0]}{2}$$

Then,

$$Y[-2] - 4Y[-1] = 4a - 2b + Y[0] - 4a + 4b - 4Y[0]$$

$$Y[-2] - 4Y[-1] = 2b - 3Y[0]$$

$$b = \frac{Y[-2] - 4Y[-1] + 3Y[0]}{2}$$

Finally,

$$Y_{\text{Set 4 of 5}}[y] = \left(\frac{Y[-2] - 2Y[-1] + Y[0]}{2} \right) y^2 + \left(\frac{Y[-2] - 4Y[-1] + 3Y[0]}{2} \right) y + Y[0]$$

6.5. Set 5 of 5:

Considering,

$$\text{for } y_3 = -1, \text{ then } Y[-1] = a - b + c$$

$$\text{for } y_2 = -2, \text{ then } Y[-2] = 4a - 2b + c$$

$$\text{for } y_1 = -3, \text{ then } Y[-3] = 9a - 3b + c$$

Then,

$$Y[-2] - Y[-1] = 4a - 2b + c - a + b - c = 3a - b$$

$$b = 3a - Y[-2] + Y[-1]$$

Then,

$$Y[-3] = 9a - 3b + c = 9a - 3(3a - Y[-2] + Y[-1]) + c$$

$$= 3Y[-2] - 3Y[-1] + c$$

$$Y[-2] = 4a - 2b + c = 4a - 2(3a - Y[-2] + Y[-1]) + c$$

$$= 4a - 6a + 2Y[-2] - 2Y[-1] + c = -2a + 2Y[-2] - 2Y[-1] + c$$

$$Y[-3] - Y[-2] = 3Y[-2] - 3Y[-1] + c - (-2a + 2Y[-2] - 2Y[-1] + c)$$

$$= 3Y[-2] - 3Y[-1] + c + 2a - 2Y[-2] + 2Y[-1] - c$$

$$= Y[-2] - Y[-1] + 2a$$

$$a = \frac{Y[-3] - 2Y[-2] + Y[-1]}{2}$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
b &= 3a - Y[-2] + Y[-1] = 3\left(\frac{Y[-3] - 2Y[-2] + Y[-1]}{2}\right) - Y[-2] + Y[-1] \\
&= \frac{3Y[-3] - 6Y[-2] + 3Y[-1] - 2Y[-2] + 2Y[-1]}{2} \\
b &= \frac{3Y[-3] - 8Y[-2] + 5Y[-1]}{2}
\end{aligned}$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
c &= x_3 - a + b = Y[-1] - \frac{Y[-3] - 2Y[-2] + Y[-1]}{2} + \frac{3Y[-3] - 8Y[-2] + 5Y[-1]}{2} \\
c &= \frac{2Y[-1] - Y[-3] + 2Y[-2] - Y[-1] + 3Y[-3] - 8Y[-2] + 5Y[-1]}{2} \\
c &= \frac{2Y[-3] - 6Y[-2] + 6Y[-1]}{2}
\end{aligned}$$

Finally,

$$Y_{Set\ 5\ of\ 5}[y] = \left(\frac{Y[-3] - 2Y[-2] + Y[-1]}{2}\right)y^2 + \left(\frac{3Y[-3] - 8Y[-2] + 5Y[-1]}{2}\right)y + Y[-3] - 3Y[-2] + 3Y[-1]$$

If we set ($y_1 = -4; y_2 = -3; y_3 = -2$), we obtain the same coefficient $a = \frac{Y[1] - 2Y[2] + Y[3]}{2}$ but more complex terms for coefficients b and c than the terms in the last set 5 of 5 ($y_1 = -3; y_2 = -2; y_3 = -1$).

Therefore, let us stop here the analysis.

6.6. The conclusion from all sets.

The simplest general quadratic equation is:

$$Y_{Set\ 3\ of\ 5}[y] = Y[y] = \left(\frac{Y[-1] - 2Y[0] + Y[1]}{2}\right)y^2 + \left(\frac{Y[1] - Y[-1]}{2}\right)y + Y[0]$$

In conclusion, we do have the simplest general equation of a quadratic function.

We may apply this same reasoning to any polynomial equation to any degree.

7. Definition of Offset $f = 0$.

Let us define the absolute value for offset $f = 0$ in any polynomial sequence as the one with the simplest polynomial equation of all.

Consequently, the closest to 0 indexes $y = \{-n, \dots, -3, -2, -1, 0, +1, +2, +3, \dots, +n\}$ produce elements $x = Y[y]$ with the lowest, or higher if change signal, value. The resulting sequence with those indexes will be the offset $f = 0$ sequence.

The simplest equation of the polynomial sequence is a natural reference.

When we consider this mathematical reference to set up the standard offset $f = 0$, we can always use a standard range index from the index 0.

In this way, when needed, we can always transform the sequence or polynomial equation to offset $f = 0$.

Seeing a polynomial sequence at offset $f = 0$ is a reference for making comparisons between sequences.

7.1. General quadratic equation, including offset.

Let us define the quadratic equation in offset $f = 0$ as follows:

$$Y_{f=0}[y] = Y_{offset=0}[y] = Y_{-0.5 < y_{sp} \leq 0.5}[y] = Y^0[y] = ay^2 + b^0y + c^0$$

Then,

$$y_{sp@offset=0} = -\frac{b^0}{2a}$$

$$x_{sp@offset=0} = \frac{-\Delta}{4a} = -\frac{b^{0^2} - 4ac^0}{4a}$$

So,

$$x_{offset \neq zero} = a(y + h)^2 + b^0(y + h) + c^0$$

$$x_{offset \neq zero} = a(y^2 + h^2 + 2hy) + b^0y + b^0h + c^0$$

$$x_{offset \neq zero} = ay^2 + ah^2 + 2ahy + b^0y + b^0h + c^0$$

$$x_{offset \neq zero} = ay^2 + (2ahy + b^0y) + (ah^2 + b^0h + c^0)$$

which results in the general offset equation concerning the coefficients of offset $f = 0$:

$$x_{offset \neq zero} = ay^2 + (b^0 + 2ah)y + (ah^2 + b^0h + c^0)$$

When we apply offset, there is no alteration in coefficient a . Now, the new b and c coefficients are:

$$b = b^0 + 2a^0h$$

$$c = a^0h^2 + b^0h + c^0$$

$$y_{sp@offset \neq 0} = -\frac{b}{2a} = -\frac{b^0 + 2a^0h}{2a^0} = -\frac{b^0}{2a} - h$$

$$y_{sp@offset \neq 0} = y_{sp@offset=0} - h$$

$$x_{sp@offset \neq 0} = x_{sp@offset=0}$$

$$-\frac{b^2 - 4ac}{4a} = -\frac{b^{0^2} - 4ac^0}{4a}$$

$$b^2 - 4ac = b^{0^2} - 4ac^0$$

$$(2ah + b^0)^2 - 4a(ah^2 + b^0h + c^0) = b^{0^2} - 4ac^0$$

$$4a^2h^2 + b^{o2} + 4ahb^o - 4a^2h^2 - 4ab^oh - 4ac^o = b^{o2} - 4ac^o$$

$$4a^2h^2 + b^{o2} + 4ahb^o - 4a^2h^2 - 4ab^oh - 4ac^o = b^{o2} - 4ac^o$$

$$0 = 0$$

From the $y_{sp@offset \neq 0} = -\frac{b^o}{2a} - h = y_{sp@offset \neq 0} - h$ equation, we can see that as we increase $h > 0$, the value of $y_{sp@offset \neq 0}$ will decrease from $y_{sp@offset=0}$.

Therefore, if we want the offset parameter to follow the y_{sp} direction, we must change the signal between offset f and Taylor shift parameter h :

$$offset = f = -h$$

From the general offset equation, $x_{offset \neq zer} = ay^2 + (b^o + 2ah)y + (ah^2 + b^oh + c^o)$, substituting $h = -f$, we have:

$$x = a^o y^2 + (b^o - 2a^o f)y + (a^o f^2 - b^o f + c^o)$$

We will have:

$$y_{sp} = -\frac{b^o - 2a^o f}{2a^o}$$

$$y_{sp} = f - \frac{b^o}{2a}$$

And,

$$x_{sp} = -\frac{\Delta}{4a} = -\frac{(b^o - 2af)^2 - 4a(af^2 - b^o f + c^o)}{4a} = \frac{4a(af^2 - b^o f + c^o) - (b^o - 2af)^2}{4a}$$

$$= \frac{4a^2 f^2 - 4ab^o f + 4ac^o - (b^{o2} - 4ab^o f + 4a^2 f^2)}{4a}$$

$$= \frac{4a^2 f^2 - 4ab^o f + 4ac^o - b^{o2} + 4ab^o f - 4a^2 f^2}{4a}$$

$$= \frac{4a^2 f^2 - 4ab^o f + 4ac^o - b^{o2} + 4ab^o f - 4a^2 f^2}{4a} = \frac{4ac^o - b^{o2}}{4a}$$

$$x_{sp} = -\frac{b^{o2} - 4ac^o}{4a} = c^o - \frac{b^{o2}}{4a}$$

From the x_{sp} and y_{sp} equations above, we can deduct:

- Once a , b^o and c^o are fixed values, x_{sp} is a fixed value for any offset.
- Only y_{sp} varies as a function of offset f .
- Starting from the symmetry point, when moving on the quadratic curve along one of the two directions, we will increase or decrease the value of the index y along the Y-axis. In any of the quadratics of our example, we will always arrive exactly at the same values of x . This means that any offset generates the same sequence of integer numbers.

7.2. Offset possibilities.

Purposely, we have an example with a quadratic integer sequence with 2 simplest equations:

1. $x = y^2 - y$ from the symmetry point ($x_{sp} = -0.25$; $y_{sp} = 0.5$), we obtain the sequence $(0, 2, 6, 12, 20, \dots)$, and
2. $x = y^2 + y$ from the symmetry point ($x_{sp} = -0.25$; $y_{sp} = -0.5$), we obtain the same sequence $(0, 2, 6, 12, 20, \dots)$.

We must define only one equation as being *offset* = $f = 0$. Which alternative to choose as to offset $f = 0$? How to choose?

Option 1:

If we define $x = y^2 + y$ with $y_{sp} = -0.5$ as being *offset* = $f = 0$, then $x = y^2 - y$ with $y_{sp} = 0.5$ would have *offset* = $f = 1$.

Consequently, the full set would be as follows:

- In the curve $x = y^2 - 7y + 12$ we have $y_{sp} = 3.5$ and $f = 4$. Sequence $(0, 2, 6, 12, 20, \dots)$ will appear in index sequence $4 \leq y < \infty$.
- In the curve $x = y^2 - 5y + 6$ we have $y_{sp} = 2.5$ and $f = 3$. Sequence $(0, 2, 6, 12, 20, \dots)$ will appear in index sequence $3 \leq y < \infty$.
- In the curve $x = y^2 - 3y + 2$ we have $y_{sp} = 1.5$ and $f = 2$. Sequence $(0, 2, 6, 12, 20, \dots)$ will appear in index sequence $2 \leq y < \infty$.
- In the curve $x = y^2 - y$ we have $y_{sp} = 0.5$ and $f = 1$. Sequence $(0, 2, 6, 12, 20, \dots)$ will appear in index sequence $1 \leq y < \infty$.
- In the curve $x = y^2 + y$ we have $y_{sp} = -0.5$ and $f = 0$. Sequence $(0, 2, 6, 12, 20, \dots)$ will appear in index sequence $0 \leq y < \infty$.
- In the curve $x = y^2 + 3y + 12$ we have $y_{sp} = -1.5$ and $f = -1$. Sequence $(0, 2, 6, 12, 20, \dots)$ will appear in index sequence $-1 \leq y < \infty$.
- In the curve $x = y^2 + 5y + 12$ we have $y_{sp} = -2.5$ and $f = -2$. Sequence $(0, 2, 6, 12, 20, \dots)$ will appear in index sequence $-2 \leq y < \infty$.
- In the curve $x = y^2 + 7y + 12$ we have $y_{sp} = -3.5$ and $f = -3$. Sequence $(0, 2, 6, 12, 20, \dots)$ will appear in index sequence $-3 \leq y < \infty$.

In this choice, the equation is:

$$f = \text{ceiling}[y_{sp}] = \text{ceiling}\left[-\frac{b}{2a}\right] = \left\lceil -\frac{b}{2a} \right\rceil$$

Option 2:

If we define $x = y^2 - y$ with $y_{sp} = 0.5$ as being *offset* = $f = 0$, then $x = y^2 + y$ with $y_{sp} = -0.5$ would have offset $f = -1$.

Consequently, the full set would be as follows:

- In the curve $x = y^2 - 7y + 12$ we have $y_{sp} = 3.5$ and $f = 3$. Sequence $(0, 2, 6, 12, 20, \dots)$ will appear in index sequence $4 \leq y < \infty$

- In the curve $x = y^2 - 5y + 6$ we have $y_{sp} = 2.5$ and $f = 2$. Sequence $(0, 2, 6, 12, 20, \dots)$ will appear in index sequence $3 \leq y < \infty$
- In the curve $x = y^2 - 3y + 2$ we have $y_{sp} = 1.5$ and $f = 1$. Sequence $(0, 2, 6, 12, 20, \dots)$ will appear in index sequence $2 \leq y < \infty$
- In the curve $x = y^2 - y$ we have $y_{sp} = 0.5$ and $f = 0$. Sequence $(0, 2, 6, 12, 20, \dots)$ will appear in index sequence $1 \leq y < \infty$
- In the curve $x = y^2 + y$ we have $y_{sp} = -0.5$ and $f = -1$. Sequence $(0, 2, 6, 12, 20, \dots)$ will appear in index sequence $0 \leq y < \infty$
- In the curve $x = y^2 + 3y + 12$ we have $y_{sp} = -1.5$ and $f = -2$. Sequence $(0, 2, 6, 12, 20, \dots)$ will appear in index sequence $-1 \leq y < \infty$
- In the curve $x = y^2 + 5y + 12$ we have $y_{sp} = -2.5$ and $f = -3$. Sequence $(0, 2, 6, 12, 20, \dots)$ will appear in index sequence $-2 \leq y < \infty$
- In the curve $x = y^2 + 7y + 12$ we have $y_{sp} = -3.5$ and $f = -4$. Sequence $(0, 2, 6, 12, 20, \dots)$ will appear in index sequence $-3 \leq y < \infty$

In this choice, the equation is:

$$f = \text{floor}[y_{sp}] = \text{floor}\left[-\frac{b}{2a}\right] = \left\lfloor -\frac{b}{2a} \right\rfloor$$

When we refer to the offset of a quadratic integer sequence generated by equations $Y_1[y] = ay^2 + b_1y + c_1$ and $Y_2[y] = ay^2 + b_2y + c_2$, we just mean that there is a displacement of the terms (elements of the sequence) generated on the X-axis in the function of index y .

In the XY-plane, the offset between two identical sequences is equivalent to moving the quadratic curve only along the Y-axis in an integer shift (integer h step) without moving the curve along the X-axis.

Remembering the example of odd numbers in the introduction, we want our sequence to appear using Tally counting.

Therefore, the only possibility where we will have y_{sp} the closest to zero and we can count the indexes y as the Tally counting is just this second possibility $x = y^2 - y$.

7.3. Offset behavior.

Therefore, from the definition “offset $f = 0$ is the polynomial equation which results in y_{sp} positive closest as possible to $y = 0$ ”, we expect to see this behavior in yellow:

y_{sp}	$\text{floor}[y_{sp}]$	$\text{ceiling}[y_{sp}]$	$\text{round}[y_{sp}]$	Function Expected
3.5	3	4	4	3
3.25	3	4	3	3
3	3	3	3	3
2.75	2	3	3	3
2.5	2	3	3	2
2.25	2	3	2	2
2	2	2	2	2
1.75	1	2	2	2
1.5	1	2	2	1
1.25	1	2	1	1
1	1	1	1	1
0.75	0	1	1	1
0.5	0	1	1	0
0.25	0	1	0	0
0	0	0	0	0
-0.25	-1	0	0	0
-0.5	-1	0	0	-1
-0.75	-1	0	-1	-1
-1	-1	-1	-1	-1
-1.25	-2	-1	-1	-1
-1.5	-2	-1	-1	-2
-1.75	-2	-1	-2	-2
-2	-2	-2	-2	-2
-2.25	-3	-2	-2	-2
-2.5	-3	-2	-2	-3
-2.75	-3	-2	-3	-3
-3	-3	-3	-3	-3
-3.25	-4	-3	-3	-3
-3.5	-4	-3	-3	-4

C002811 Figure 1. Search for the correct equation function (in yellow) for the offset.

In conclusion, there is no staircase function with step 1 to express exactly the offset behavior.

We need to introduce a new staircase mathematical function to produce the offset of any polynomial integer sequence.

8. The “round half to zero (roundz)” staircase function.

The closest equation to the desired result would be the round function.

The problem with the round function appears when $y_{sp} = 0.5$ or any other value in the form of $y_{sp} = \frac{\text{Odd}}{2}$.

We need $f = 0$ for $(-0.5 < y_{sp} \leq 0.5)$. Then, the offset f for $y_{sp} = 0.5$ is $f = 0$. However, $\text{round}[0.5] = 1$.

Therefore, we must change the round function to meet the offset $f = 0$ for the entire range $-0.5 < y_{sp} \leq +0.5$.

$$\text{Offset} = f = 0 \text{ when } -0.5 < \left(y_{sp} (@\text{offset} = 0) = -\frac{b}{2a} \right) \leq +0.5$$

Let us create a new equation function called “round half to zero”, abbreviated as “roundz”, defined as:

$$\text{roundz}[y_{sp}] = 0 \text{ for } (-0.5 < y_{sp} \leq 0.5)$$

Then, we will meet the desired behavior $f = 0$ when $-0.5 < -\frac{b}{2a} \leq +0.5$.

Expanding, we have:

- ...
- $f = 3$ when $2.5 < -\frac{b}{2a} \leq 3.5$
- $f = 2$ when $1.5 < -\frac{b}{2a} \leq 2.5$
- $f = 1$ when $0.5 < -\frac{b}{2a} \leq 1.5$
- $f = 0$ when $-0.5 < -\frac{b}{2a} \leq 0.5$
- $f = -1$ when $-1.5 < -\frac{b}{2a} \leq -0.5$
- $f = -2$ when $-2.5 < -\frac{b}{2a} \leq -1.5$
- $f = -3$ when $-3.5 < -\frac{b}{2a} \leq -2.5$
- ...

In the computer, these calculations are almost equivalent to using the function round. We just need to subtract the smallest computer infinitesimal number to meet the new round half to zero (roundz) function.

For $m = \text{integer}$, the round function is:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{round}[m + 0.5] &= m + 1 \\ \text{round}[m - 0.5] &= m \\ \text{round}\left[\frac{2k + 1}{2}\right] &= k + 1 \\ \text{round}\left[\frac{2k - 1}{2}\right] &= k \end{aligned}$$

For $m = \text{integer}$, the new roundz function is:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{roundz}[m + 0.5] &= m \\ \text{roundz}[m - 0.5] &= m - 1 \\ \text{roundz}\left[\frac{2k + 1}{2}\right] &= k \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{roundz} \left[\frac{2k-1}{2} \right] = k-1$$

C002811 Figure 2. C001410 The roundz function.

9. Formal quadratics offset equation.

From now on, we will define the equation of a quadratic offset as:

$$\text{offset} = f = \text{roundz} \left[-\frac{b}{2a} \right] = \text{round} \left[-\frac{b}{2a} - \text{infinitesimal} \right]$$

We can say:

$$\text{offset} = f = \text{round} \left[-\frac{b}{2a} - \varepsilon \right] = \text{round} \left[f - \frac{b^0}{2a} - \varepsilon \right]$$

Using the new function roundz (round half to zero) function:

$$offset = f = roundz \left[-\frac{b}{2a} \right] = roundz \left[f - \frac{b^0}{2a} \right]$$

See below the map of all possible real values for the y_{sp} coordinate in quadratics because of all combinations of integer coefficients a and b .

In the pink vertical column, we list the coefficient a . In the purple horizontal row, we list the coefficient b .

a \ b	-10	-9	-8	-7	-6	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
10	0.50	0.45	0.40	0.35	0.30	0.25	0.20	0.15	0.10	0.05	0	-0.05	-0.10	-0.15	-0.20	-0.25	-0.30	-0.35	-0.40	-0.45	-0.50
9	0.56	0.50	0.44	0.39	0.33	0.28	0.22	0.17	0.11	0.06	0	-0.06	-0.11	-0.17	-0.22	-0.28	-0.33	-0.39	-0.44	-0.50	-0.56
8	0.63	0.56	0.50	0.44	0.38	0.31	0.25	0.19	0.13	0.06	0	-0.06	-0.13	-0.19	-0.25	-0.31	-0.38	-0.44	-0.50	-0.56	-0.63
7	0.71	0.64	0.57	0.50	0.43	0.36	0.29	0.21	0.14	0.07	0	-0.07	-0.14	-0.21	-0.29	-0.36	-0.43	-0.50	-0.57	-0.64	-0.71
6	0.83	0.75	0.67	0.58	0.50	0.42	0.33	0.25	0.17	0.08	0	-0.08	-0.17	-0.25	-0.33	-0.42	-0.50	-0.58	-0.67	-0.75	-0.83
5	1.00	0.90	0.80	0.70	0.60	0.50	0.40	0.30	0.20	0.10	0	-0.10	-0.20	-0.30	-0.40	-0.50	-0.60	-0.70	-0.80	-0.90	-1.00
4	1.25	1.13	1.00	0.88	0.75	0.63	0.50	0.38	0.25	0.13	0	-0.13	-0.25	-0.38	-0.50	-0.63	-0.75	-0.88	-1.00	-1.13	-1.25
3	1.67	1.50	1.33	1.17	1.00	0.83	0.67	0.50	0.33	0.17	0	-0.17	-0.33	-0.50	-0.67	-0.83	-1.00	-1.17	-1.33	-1.50	-1.67
2	2.50	2.25	2.00	1.75	1.50	1.25	1.00	0.75	0.50	0.25	0	-0.25	-0.50	-0.75	-1.00	-1.25	-1.50	-1.75	-2.00	-2.25	-2.50
1	5.00	4.50	4.00	3.50	3.00	2.50	2.00	1.50	1.00	0.50	0	-0.50	-1.00	-1.50	-2.00	-2.50	-3.00	-3.50	-4.00	-4.50	-5.00
0																					
-1	-5.00	-4.50	-4.00	-3.50	-3.00	-2.50	-2.00	-1.50	-1.00	-0.50	0	0.50	1.00	1.50	2.00	2.50	3.00	3.50	4.00	4.50	5.00
-2	-2.50	-2.25	-2.00	-1.75	-1.50	-1.25	-1.00	-0.75	-0.50	-0.25	0	0.25	0.50	0.75	1.00	1.25	1.50	1.75	2.00	2.25	2.50
-3	-1.67	-1.50	-1.33	-1.17	-1.00	-0.83	-0.67	-0.50	-0.33	-0.17	0	0.17	0.33	0.50	0.67	0.83	1.00	1.17	1.33	1.50	1.67
-4	-1.25	-1.13	-1.00	-0.88	-0.75	-0.63	-0.50	-0.38	-0.25	-0.13	0	0.13	0.25	0.38	0.50	0.63	0.75	0.88	1.00	1.13	1.25
-5	-1.00	-0.90	-0.80	-0.70	-0.60	-0.50	-0.40	-0.30	-0.20	-0.10	0	0.10	0.20	0.30	0.40	0.50	0.60	0.70	0.80	0.90	1.00
-6	-0.83	-0.75	-0.67	-0.58	-0.50	-0.42	-0.33	-0.25	-0.17	-0.08	0	0.08	0.17	0.25	0.33	0.42	0.50	0.58	0.67	0.75	0.83
-7	-0.71	-0.64	-0.57	-0.50	-0.43	-0.36	-0.29	-0.21	-0.14	-0.07	0	0.07	0.14	0.21	0.29	0.36	0.43	0.50	0.57	0.64	0.71
-8	-0.63	-0.56	-0.50	-0.44	-0.38	-0.31	-0.25	-0.19	-0.13	-0.06	0	0.06	0.13	0.19	0.25	0.31	0.38	0.44	0.50	0.56	0.63
-9	-0.56	-0.50	-0.44	-0.39	-0.33	-0.28	-0.22	-0.17	-0.11	-0.06	0	0.06	0.11	0.17	0.22	0.28	0.33	0.39	0.44	0.50	0.56
-10	-0.50	-0.45	-0.40	-0.35	-0.30	-0.25	-0.20	-0.15	-0.10	-0.05	0	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20	0.25	0.30	0.35	0.40	0.45	0.50

C002811 Figure 3. The green cells show the quadratic symmetry point Y -coordinate $y_{sp} = -\frac{b}{2a}$ with the (integer + 0.5) value.

If $b = \text{even} = 2n$, then $-\frac{b}{2a} = -\frac{2n}{2a} = -\frac{n}{a}$ may be an integer.

If $b = \text{odd} = 2n - 1$, $-\frac{b}{2a} = -\frac{2n-1}{2a} = -\frac{n}{a} + \frac{1}{2a}$ will never be an integer.

The integers and the $\frac{\text{odd}}{2}$ numbers form the same map as the MID – Map of Integers and Divisors.

Now, applying the roundz staircase function, we obtain all results as integer numbers:

a \ b	-10	-9	-8	-7	-6	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1
9	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	-1
8	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	-1	-1
7	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1
6	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1
5	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1
4	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1
3	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-2	-2
2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	-2	-2	-2	-2	-3	-3
1	5	4	4	3	3	2	2	1	1	0	0	-1	-1	-2	-2	-3	-3	-4	-4	-5	-5	-5
0																						
-1	-5	-5	-4	-4	-3	-3	-2	-2	-1	-1	0	0	1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4	5	5
-2	-3	-2	-2	-2	-2	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2
-3	-2	-2	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2
-4	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
-5	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
-6	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
-7	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1
-8	-1	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
-9	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
-10	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

C002811 Figure 4. The quadratic offset $f = \text{roundz} \left[-\frac{b}{2a} \right]$.

10. Symmetry Point (sp) in polynomials.

Let us define the symmetry point (sp) of a polynomial curve as the point on the polynomial curve that divides the curve into 2 parts as symmetrically as possible.

We denote a symmetry point as being the point $sp = (x_{sp}, y_{sp})$. The coordinates of the symmetry point in the XY plane are x_{sp} and y_{sp} .

To define the formula for the coordinates (x_{sp}, y_{sp}) of the symmetry point, we use the results obtained from the Taylor shift.

10.1. Symmetry point coordinates from the offset properties.

Notice that if we want to have a symmetric polynomial of any degree d , we just may do:

$$Yd[y] = a_d y^d$$

This means that any Taylor shift h in this curve results in:

$$\begin{aligned} Y^o[y] &= Y[y + h] \\ &= a_d y^d + d a_d h y^{d-1} + \frac{d(d-1)}{2} a_d h^2 y^{d-2} + \frac{d(d-1)(d-2)}{3!} a_d h^3 y^{d-3} \\ &+ \dots + \frac{d(d-1)(d-2)}{3!} a_d h^{d-3} y^3 + \frac{d(d-1)}{2} a_d h^{d-2} y^2 + d a_d h^{d-1} y^1 \\ &+ a_d h^d \end{aligned}$$

These coefficients when integers are the Pascal's triangle coefficients.

This is an important hint that we can obtain all coefficients of the Taylor shift from Pascal's triangle. We will show how the Shaw and Traub method for the Taylor shift is fully based on Pascal's triangle.

If $h = -f = \text{integer}$, the two expressions above are the same sequence of integers. What changes is only the offset of the same curve along the Y-axis.

Then, if there is a symmetry point in each of the two curves, in any offset, this symmetry point is in the same position with respect to the integer elements of the sequence or with respect to the infinite points of the polynomial curve.

Therefore, for $h = -f = \text{integer}$, both equations:

$$\begin{aligned} Y^o[y] &= Y[y + h] \\ &= a_d (y + h)^d + a_{d-1} (y + h)^{d-1} + a_{d-2} (y + h)^{d-2} + \dots + a_3 (y + h)^3 \\ &+ a (y + h)^2 + b (y + h) + c \end{aligned}$$

Or,

$$Y[y] = a_d y^d + a_{d-1} y^{d-1} + a_{d-2} y^{d-2} + \dots + a_4 y^4 + a_3 y^3 + a y^2 + b y + c$$

Represent the same sequence of integers.

Then, let us define $sp = (x_{sp}, y_{sp})$ as the symmetry point of $Y[y]$ and $sp^o = (x_{sp^o}, y_{sp^o})$ as the symmetry point of $Y^o[y] = Y[y - f]$.

To obtain the equation for the symmetry point in any polynomial, two things must occur when we perform an offset or integer Taylor shift from $Y[y]$ with $sp = (x_{sp}, y_{sp})$ to $Y^o[y] = Y[y - f]$ with $sp^o = (x_{sp^o}, y_{sp^o})$:

$$\begin{aligned}x_{sp^o} &= x_{sp} \\y_{sp^o} &= y_{sp} + f\end{aligned}$$

Then, we must define the Y-coordinate of the symmetry point as being the value of y when:

$$Y^{[d-1]}[y] = \frac{d^{d-1}}{dy^{d-1}}(Y[y]) = 0$$

$$Y^{[d-1]}[y] = d! a_d y + (d-1)! a_{d-1}$$

and for $y = y_{sp}$:

$$d! a_d y_{sp} + (d-1)! a_{d-1} = 0$$

$$y_{sp} = -\frac{(d-1)! a_{d-1}}{d! a_d}$$

$$y_{sp} = -\frac{a_{d-1}}{d a_d}$$

And,

$$x_{sp} = Y[y_{sp}] = Y\left[-\frac{a_{d-1}}{d a_d}\right]$$

So,

$$\text{symmetry point} = sp = (x_{sp}, y_{sp}) = \left(Y\left[-\frac{a_{d-1}}{d a_d}\right], -\frac{a_{d-1}}{d a_d}\right)$$

Note that whatever the polynomial, the symmetry point will always be close to the smallest element or elements (or the largest if the sign of the entire elements of the sequence are inverted).

11. Taylor shift, symmetry point (sp) and Pascal's triangle.

Let us better understand the dynamics of the symmetry point, the symmetry of the Taylor shift equation, and the symmetry in Pascal's triangle.

11.1. Taylor shift for 1st degree polynomials.

$$Y1[y] = by + c$$

$$Y^{[1]}1[y] = b$$

Then,

$$Y1[y + h] = Y^{[1]}[h]y + Y[h]$$

$$Y1[y + h] = by + bh + c$$

Then,

$b^{\circ} = b$	$b = b^{\circ}$
$c^{\circ} = bh + c$	$c = -bh + c^{\circ}$

Symmetry point:

$$y_{sp} = -\frac{a_{d-1}}{da_d} = -\frac{c}{b}$$

$$x_{sp} = Y1\left[-\frac{c}{b}\right] = b\left(-\frac{c}{b}\right) + c = 0$$

$$sp_{Y1[y]} = (x_{sp}, y_{sp}) = \left(0, -\frac{c}{b}\right)$$

11.2. Taylor shift for 2nd degree polynomials.

$$Y2[y] = ay^2 + by + c$$

$$Y^{[1]}2[y] = 2ay + b$$

$$Y^{[2]}2[y] = 2a$$

Then,

$$Y2[y + h] = \frac{Y^{[2]}[h]}{2!}y^2 + Y^{[1]}[h]y + Y[h]$$

$$Y2[y + h] = \frac{2a}{2!}y^2 + (2ah + b)y + ah^2 + bh + c$$

$$Y2[y + h] = ay^2 + (2ah + b)y + ah^2 + bh + c$$

Then,

$a^{\circ} = a$	$a = a^{\circ}$
$b^{\circ} = b + 2ah$	$b = b^{\circ} - 2ah$
$c^{\circ} = ah^2 + bh + c$	$c = a^{\circ}h^2 - b^{\circ}h + c^{\circ}$

Symmetry point:

$$y_{sp} = -\frac{a_{d-1}}{da_d} = -\frac{b}{2a}$$

$$x_{sp} = Y2\left[-\frac{b}{2a}\right] = a\left(-\frac{b}{2a}\right)^2 + b\left(-\frac{b}{2a}\right) + c = \frac{b^2}{4a} - \frac{b^2}{2a} + c = \frac{-b^2 + 4ac}{4a}$$

$$sp_{Y2[y]} = (x_{sp}, y_{sp}) = \left(-\frac{b^2 - 4ac}{4a}, -\frac{b}{2a} \right)$$

11.3. Taylor shift for 3rd degree polynomials.

$$\begin{aligned} Y3[y] &= a_3y^3 + ay^2 + by + c \\ Y^{[1]}3[y] &= 3a_3y^2 + 2ay + b \\ Y^{[2]}3[y] &= 6a_3y + 2a \\ Y^{[3]}3[y] &= 6a_3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} Y3[y+h] &= \frac{Y^{[3]}[h]}{3!}y^3 + \frac{Y^{[2]}[h]}{2!}y^2 + Y^{[1]}[h]y + Y[h] \\ Y3[y+h] &= \frac{6a_3}{3!}y^3 + \frac{6a_3h + 2a}{2!}y^2 + (3a_3h^2 + 2ah + b)y + a_3h^3 + ah^2 + bh + c \\ Y3[y+h] &= a_3y^3 + (3a_3h + a)y^2 + (3a_3h^2 + 2ah + b)y + a_3h^3 + ah^2 + bh + c \end{aligned}$$

Doing $h = f = \text{integer}$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} a^\circ &= 3a_3h + a \\ a &= a^\circ - 3a_3^\circ h \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} b^\circ &= 3a_3h^2 + 2ah + b \\ b &= -3a_3h^2 - 2ah + b^\circ \\ b &= -3a_3^\circ h^2 - 2(a^\circ - 3a_3^\circ h)h + b^\circ \\ b &= -3a_3^\circ h^2 - 2a^\circ h + 6a_3^\circ h^2 + b^\circ \\ b &= 3a_3^\circ h^2 - 2a^\circ h + b^\circ \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} c^\circ &= a_3h^3 + ah^2 + bh + c \\ c &= -a_3h^3 - ah^2 - bh + c^\circ \\ c &= -a_3^\circ h^3 - (a^\circ - 3a_3^\circ h)h^2 - (3a_3^\circ h^2 - 2a^\circ h + b^\circ)h + c^\circ \\ c &= -a_3^\circ h^3 - a^\circ h^2 + 3a_3^\circ h^3 - 3a_3^\circ h^3 + 2a^\circ h^2 - b^\circ h + c^\circ \\ c &= -a_3^\circ h^3 + a^\circ h^2 - b^\circ h + c^\circ \end{aligned}$$

Then,

$a_3^\circ = a_3$	$a_3 = a_3^\circ$
$a^\circ = 3a_3h + a$	$a = a^\circ - 3a_3^\circ h$
$b^\circ = 3a_3h^2 + 2ah + b$	$b = 3a_3^\circ h^2 - 2a^\circ h + b^\circ$
$c^\circ = a_3h^3 + ah^2 + bh + c$	$c = -a_3^\circ h^3 + a^\circ h^2 - b^\circ h + c^\circ$

Symmetry point:

$$\begin{aligned} y_{sp} &= -\frac{a_{d-1}}{da_d} = -\frac{a}{3a_3} \\ x_{sp} &= Y3\left[-\frac{a}{3a_3}\right] = a_3\left(-\frac{a}{3a_3}\right)^3 + a\left(-\frac{a}{3a_3}\right)^2 + b\left(-\frac{a}{3a_3}\right) + c \end{aligned}$$

$$x_{sp} = -\frac{a^3}{27a_3^2} + \frac{a^3}{9a_3^2} - \frac{ab}{3a_3} + c$$

$$sp_{Y_3[y]} = (x_{sp}, y_{sp}) = \left(-\frac{a^3}{27a_3^2} + \frac{a^3}{9a_3^2} - \frac{ab}{3a_3} + c, -\frac{a}{3a_3} \right)$$

11.4. Taylor shift for 4th degree polynomials.

$$Y_4[y] = a_4y^4 + a_3y^3 + ay^2 + by + c$$

$$Y^{[1]}_4[y] = 4a_4y^3 + 3a_3y^2 + 2ay + b$$

$$Y^{[2]}_4[y] = 12a_4y^2 + 6a_3y + 2a$$

$$Y^{[3]}_4[y] = 24a_4y + 6a_3$$

$$Y^{[4]}_4[y] = 24a_4$$

$$Y_4[y+h] = \frac{Y^{[4]}[h]}{4!}y^4 + \frac{Y^{[3]}[h]}{3!}y^3 + \frac{Y^{[2]}[h]}{2!}y^2 + Y^{[1]}[h]y + Y[h]$$

$$Y_4[y+h] = \frac{24a_4}{4!}y^4 + \frac{24a_4h + 6a_3}{3!}y^3 + \frac{12a_4h^2 + 6a_3h + 2a}{2!}y^2$$

$$+ (4a_4h^3 + 3a_3h^2 + 2ah + b)y + a_4h^4 + a_3h^3 + ah^2 + bh + c$$

$$Y_4[y+h] = a_4y^4 + (4a_4h + a_3)y^3 + (6a_4h^2 + 3a_3h + a)y^2$$

$$+ (4a_4h^3 + 3a_3h^2 + 2ah + b)y + a_4h^4 + a_3h^3 + ah^2 + bh + c$$

$$a_3^{\circ} = 4a_4h + a_3$$

$$a_3 = -4a_4^{\circ}h + a_3^{\circ}$$

$$a^{\circ} = 6a_4h^2 + 3a_3h + a$$

$$a = a^{\circ} - 6a_4h^2 - 3a_3h$$

$$a = a^{\circ} - 6a_4^{\circ}h^2 - 3(a_3^{\circ} - 4a_4^{\circ}h)h$$

$$a = a^{\circ} - 6a_4^{\circ}h^2 - 3a_3^{\circ}h + 12a_4^{\circ}h^2$$

$$a = 6a_4^{\circ}h^2 - 3a_3^{\circ}h + a^{\circ}$$

$$b^{\circ} = 4a_4h^3 + 3a_3h^2 + 2ah + b$$

$$b = -4a_4h^3 - 3a_3h^2 - 2ah + b^{\circ}$$

$$b = -4a_4^{\circ}h^3 - 3(-4a_4^{\circ}h + a_3^{\circ})h^2 - 2(6a_4^{\circ}h^2 - 3a_3^{\circ}h + a^{\circ})h + b^{\circ}$$

$$b = -4a_4^{\circ}h^3 + 12a_4^{\circ}h^3 - 3a_3^{\circ}h^2 - 12a_4^{\circ}h^3 + 6a_3^{\circ}h^2 - 2a^{\circ}h + b^{\circ}$$

$$b = -4a_4^{\circ}h^3 + 3a_3^{\circ}h^2 - 2a^{\circ}h + b^{\circ}$$

$$c^{\circ} = a_4h^4 + a_3h^3 + ah^2 + bh + c$$

$$c = -a_4h^4 - a_3h^3 - ah^2 - bh + c^{\circ}$$

$$c = -a_4^{\circ}h^4 - (-4a_4^{\circ}h + a_3^{\circ})h^3 - (6a_4^{\circ}h^2 - 3a_3^{\circ}h + a^{\circ})h^2$$

$$- (-4a_4^{\circ}h^3 + 3a_3^{\circ}h^2 - 2a^{\circ}h + b^{\circ})h + c^{\circ}$$

$$c = -a_4^{\circ}h^4 + 4a_4^{\circ}h^4 - a_3^{\circ}h^3 - 6a_4^{\circ}h^4 + 3a_3^{\circ}h^3 - a^{\circ}h^2 + 4a_4^{\circ}h^4 - 3a_3^{\circ}h^3 + 2a^{\circ}h^2 - b^{\circ}h$$

$$+ c^{\circ}$$

$$c = a_4^{\circ}h^4 - a_3^{\circ}h^3 + a^{\circ}h^2 - b^{\circ}h + c^{\circ}$$

$a_4^{\circ} = a_4$	$a_4 = a_4^{\circ}$
---------------------	---------------------

$a_3^{\circ} = 4a_4h + a_3$	$a_3 = -4a_4^{\circ}h + a_3^{\circ}$
$a^{\circ} = 6a_4h^2 + 3a_3h + a$	$a = 6a_4^{\circ}h^2 - 3a_3^{\circ}h + a^{\circ}$
$b^{\circ} = 4a_4h^3 + 3a_3h^2 + 2ah + b$	$b = -4a_4^{\circ}h^3 + 3a_3^{\circ}h^2 - 2a^{\circ}h + b^{\circ}$
$c^{\circ} = a_4h^4 + a_3h^3 + ah^2 + bh + c$	$c = a_4^{\circ}h^4 - a_3^{\circ}h^3 + a^{\circ}h^2 - b^{\circ}h + c^{\circ}$

Symmetry point:

$$y_{sp} = -\frac{a_{d-1}}{da_d} = -\frac{a_3}{4a_4}$$

$$x_{sp} = Y4\left[-\frac{a_3}{4a_4}\right] = a_4\left(-\frac{a_3}{4a_4}\right)^4 + a_3\left(-\frac{a_3}{4a_4}\right)^3 + a\left(-\frac{a_3}{4a_4}\right)^2 + b\left(-\frac{a_3}{4a_4}\right) + c$$

$$x_{sp} = \frac{a_3^4}{256a_4^3} - \frac{a_3^4}{64a_4^3} + \frac{a_3^2a}{16a_4^2} - \frac{a_3b}{4a_4} + c$$

$$sp_{Y4[y]} = (x_{sp}, y_{sp}) = \left(\frac{a_3^4}{256a_4^3} - \frac{a_3^4}{64a_4^3} + \frac{a_3^2a}{16a_4^2} - \frac{a_3b}{4a_4} + c, -\frac{a_3}{4a_4}\right)$$

11.5. Taylor shift for 5th degree polynomials.

$$Y5[y] = a_5y^5 + a_4y^4 + a_3y^3 + ay^2 + by + c$$

$$Y^{[1]}5[y] = 5a_5y^4 + 4a_4y^3 + 3a_3y^2 + 2ay + b$$

$$Y^{[2]}5[y] = 20a_5y^3 + 12a_4y^2 + 6a_3y + 2a$$

$$Y^{[3]}5[y] = 60a_5y^2 + 24a_4y + 6a_3$$

$$Y^{[4]}5[y] = 120a_5y + 24a_4$$

$$Y^{[5]}5[y] = 120a_5$$

$$Y5[y+h] = \frac{Y^{[5]}[h]}{5!}y^5 + \frac{Y^{[4]}[h]}{4!}y^4 + \frac{Y^{[3]}[h]}{3!}y^3 + \frac{Y^{[2]}[h]}{2!}y^2 + Y^{[1]}[h]y + Y[h]$$

$$Y5[y+h] = \frac{120a_5}{5!}y^5 + \frac{120a_5h + 24a_4}{4!}y^4 + \frac{60a_5h^2 + 24a_4h + 6a_3}{3!}y^3$$

$$+ \frac{20a_5h^3 + 12a_4h^2 + 6a_3h + 2a}{2!}y^2$$

$$+ (5a_5h^4 + 4a_4h^3 + 3a_3h^2 + 2ah + b)y + a_5h^5 + a_4h^4 + a_3h^3 + ah^2 + bh + c$$

$$Y5[y+h] = a_5y^5 + (5a_5h + a_4)y^4 + (10a_5h^2 + 4a_4h + a_3)y^3$$

$$+ (10a_5h^3 + 6a_4h^2 + 3a_3h + a)y^2 + (5a_5h^4 + 4a_4h^3 + 3a_3h^2 + 2ah + b)y$$

$$+ a_5h^5 + a_4h^4 + a_3h^3 + ah^2 + bh + c$$

$a_5^{\circ} = a_5$	$a_5 = a_5^{\circ}$
$a_4^{\circ} = 5a_5h + a_4$	$a_4 = -5a_5^{\circ}h + a_4^{\circ}$
$a_3^{\circ} = 10a_5h^2 + 4a_4h + a_3$	$a_3 = 10a_5^{\circ}h^2 - 4a_4^{\circ}h + a_3^{\circ}$
$a^{\circ} = 10a_5h^3 + 6a_4h^2 + 3a_3h + a$	$a = -10a_5^{\circ}h^3 + 6a_4^{\circ}h^2 - 3a_3^{\circ}h + a^{\circ}$
$b^{\circ} = 5a_5h^4 + 4a_4h^3 + 3a_3h^2 + 2ah + b$	$b = 5a_5^{\circ}h^4 - 4a_4^{\circ}h^3 + 3a_3^{\circ}h^2 - 2a^{\circ}h + b^{\circ}$
$c^{\circ} = a_5h^5 + a_4h^4 + a_3h^3 + ah^2 + bh + c$	$c = -a_5^{\circ}h^5 + a_4^{\circ}h^4 - a_3^{\circ}h^3 + a^{\circ}h^2 - b^{\circ}h + c^{\circ}$

Symmetry point:

$$y_{sp} = -\frac{a_{d-1}}{da_d} = -\frac{a_4}{5a_5}$$

$$x_{sp} = Y5 \left[-\frac{a_4}{5a_5} \right]$$

$$= a_5 \left(-\frac{a_4}{5a_5} \right)^5 + a_4 \left(-\frac{a_4}{5a_5} \right)^4 + a_3 \left(-\frac{a_4}{5a_5} \right)^3 + a_2 \left(-\frac{a_4}{5a_5} \right)^2 + b \left(-\frac{a_4}{5a_5} \right) + c$$

$$x_{sp} = -\frac{a_4^5}{3125a_5^4} + \frac{a_4^5}{625a_5^4} - \frac{a_4^3 a_3}{125a_5^3} + \frac{a_4^2 a}{25a_5^2} - \frac{a_4 b}{5a_5} + c$$

$$sp_{Y5[y]} = (x_{sp}, y_{sp}) = \left(-\frac{a_4^5}{3125a_5^4} + \frac{a_4^5}{625a_5^4} - \frac{a_4^3 a_3}{125a_5^3} + \frac{a_4^2 a}{25a_5^2} - \frac{a_4 b}{5a_5} + c, -\frac{a_4}{5a_5} \right)$$

11.6. The Taylor shift coefficients from Pascal's triangle.

Because of the results above, see the summary of the Shaw and Traub method for the Taylor shift based on Pascal's triangle.

We start from:

$$Yd[y] = a_d y^d + a_{d-1} y^{d-1} + a_{d-2} y^{d-2} + \dots + a_4 y^4 + a_3 y^3 + a_2 y^2 + a_1 y + c$$

and shift to:

$$Y^o[y] = Yd[y + h] = a_d^o y^d + a_{d-1}^o y^{d-1} + a_{d-2}^o y^{d-2} + \dots + a_3^o y^3 + a_2^o y^2 + a_1^o y + a_0^o$$

The new coefficients come from Pascal's triangle, such as:

	https://eis.org/A000012	https://eis.org/A256958	https://eis.org/A000217	https://eis.org/A000292	https://eis.org/A000332	https://eis.org/A000389	https://eis.org/A000579	https://eis.org/A000580	https://eis.org/A000581	https://eis.org/A000582
$a^0_0 =$	1 a_0	1 ha_1	1 $h^2 a_2$	1 $h^3 a_3$	1 $h^4 a_4$	1 $h^5 a_5$	1 $h^6 a_6$	1 $h^7 a_7$	1 $h^8 a_8$	1 $h^9 a_9$
$a^0_1 =$	1 a_1	2 ha_2	3 $h^2 a_3$	4 $h^3 a_4$	5 $h^4 a_5$	6 $h^5 a_6$	7 $h^6 a_7$	8 $h^7 a_8$	9 $h^8 a_9$	10 $h^9 a_{10}$
$a^0_2 =$	1 a_2	3 ha_3	6 $h^2 a_4$	10 $h^3 a_5$	15 $h^4 a_6$	21 $h^5 a_7$	28 $h^6 a_8$	36 $h^7 a_9$	45 $h^8 a_{10}$	55 $h^9 a_{11}$
$a^0_3 =$	1 a_3	4 ha_4	10 $h^2 a_5$	20 $h^3 a_6$	35 $h^4 a_7$	56 $h^5 a_8$	84 $h^6 a_9$	120 $h^7 a_{10}$	165 $h^8 a_{11}$	220 $h^9 a_{12}$
$a^0_4 =$	1 a_4	5 ha_5	15 $h^2 a_6$	35 $h^3 a_7$	70 $h^4 a_8$	126 $h^5 a_9$	210 $h^6 a_{10}$	330 $h^7 a_{11}$	495 $h^8 a_{12}$	715 $h^9 a_{13}$
$a^0_5 =$	1 a_5	6 ha_6	21 $h^2 a_7$	56 $h^3 a_8$	126 $h^4 a_9$	252 $h^5 a_{10}$	462 $h^6 a_{11}$	792 $h^7 a_{12}$	1287 $h^8 a_{13}$	2002 $h^9 a_{14}$
$a^0_6 =$	1 a_6	7 ha_7	28 $h^2 a_8$	84 $h^3 a_9$	210 $h^4 a_{10}$	462 $h^5 a_{11}$	924 $h^6 a_{12}$	1716 $h^7 a_{13}$	3003 $h^8 a_{14}$	5005 $h^9 a_{15}$
$a^0_7 =$	1 a_7	8 ha_8	36 $h^2 a_9$	120 $h^3 a_{10}$	330 $h^4 a_{11}$	792 $h^5 a_{12}$	1716 $h^6 a_{13}$	3432 $h^7 a_{14}$	6435 $h^8 a_{15}$	11440 $h^9 a_{16}$
$a^0_8 =$	1 a_8	9 ha_9	45 $h^2 a_{10}$	165 $h^3 a_{11}$	495 $h^4 a_{12}$	1287 $h^5 a_{13}$	3003 $h^6 a_{14}$	6435 $h^7 a_{15}$	12870 $h^8 a_{16}$	24310 $h^9 a_{17}$
$a^0_9 =$	1 a_9	10 ha_{10}	55 $h^2 a_{11}$	220 $h^3 a_{12}$	715 $h^4 a_{13}$	2002 $h^5 a_{14}$	5005 $h^6 a_{15}$	11440 $h^7 a_{16}$	24310 $h^8 a_{17}$	48620 $h^9 a_{18}$
$a^0_{10} =$	1 a_{10}	11 ha_{11}	66 $h^2 a_{12}$	286 $h^3 a_{13}$	1001 $h^4 a_{14}$	3003 $h^5 a_{15}$	8008 $h^6 a_{16}$	19448 $h^7 a_{17}$	43758 $h^8 a_{18}$	92378 $h^9 a_{19}$
$a^0_{11} =$	1 a_{11}	12 ha_{12}	78 $h^2 a_{13}$	364 $h^3 a_{14}$	1365 $h^4 a_{15}$	4368 $h^5 a_{16}$	12376 $h^6 a_{17}$	31824 $h^7 a_{18}$	75582 $h^8 a_{19}$	167960 $h^9 a_{20}$
$a^0_{12} =$	1 a_{12}	13 ha_{13}	91 $h^2 a_{14}$	455 $h^3 a_{15}$	1820 $h^4 a_{16}$	6188 $h^5 a_{17}$	18564 $h^6 a_{18}$	50388 $h^7 a_{19}$	125970 $h^8 a_{20}$	293930 $h^9 a_{21}$
$a^0_{13} =$	1 a_{13}	14 ha_{14}	105 $h^2 a_{15}$	560 $h^3 a_{16}$	2380 $h^4 a_{17}$	8568 $h^5 a_{18}$	27132 $h^6 a_{19}$	77520 $h^7 a_{20}$	203490 $h^8 a_{21}$	497420 $h^9 a_{22}$
$a^0_{14} =$	1 a_{14}	15 ha_{15}	120 $h^2 a_{16}$	680 $h^3 a_{17}$	3060 $h^4 a_{18}$	11628 $h^5 a_{19}$	38760 $h^6 a_{20}$	116280 $h^7 a_{21}$	319770 $h^8 a_{22}$	817190 $h^9 a_{23}$
$a^0_{15} =$	1 a_{15}	16 ha_{16}	136 $h^2 a_{17}$	816 $h^3 a_{18}$	3876 $h^4 a_{19}$	15504 $h^5 a_{20}$	54264 $h^6 a_{21}$	170544 $h^7 a_{22}$	490314 $h^8 a_{23}$	1307504 $h^9 a_{24}$

Figure 5. C001112 The Taylor shift coefficients a_n^o as a function of the initial coefficients a_n , where $0 \leq n \leq d$. <https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/452657303057881/>.

The vertical and horizontal sequences of the coefficients above are:

<https://oeis.org/A000012>
<https://oeis.org/A256958>
<https://oeis.org/A000217>
<https://oeis.org/A000292>
<https://oeis.org/A000332>
<https://oeis.org/A000389>
<https://oeis.org/A000579>
<https://oeis.org/A000580>
<https://oeis.org/A000581>
<https://oeis.org/A000582>

Each row of the table has an infinite number of terms.

Each polynomial degree has a ladder-shaped black line on the table. The ladder-shaped black line is defined by d .

We can obtain the value of each coefficient a_n° by adding up the terms up to its black line of the table.

The number of terms we add in each row a_n° is limited by the diagonal corresponding to the degree d of the polynomial. We sum the terms of a row up to the ladder-shaped black line.

The number of terms of the sum of coefficient a_n° of a polynomial of degree d is:

$$\text{number of terms} = d - n + 1$$

where n is the coefficient number and d is the polynomial degree.

11.7. Example for $d = 6$.

$$a_6^{\circ} = 01. a_6 h^0$$

$$a_5^{\circ} = 06. a_6 h^1 + 01. a_5 h^0$$

$$a_4^{\circ} = 15. a_6 h^2 + 05. a_5 h^1 + 1. a_4 h^0$$

$$a_3^{\circ} = 20. a_6 h^3 + 10. a_5 h^2 + 4. a_4 h^1 + 1. a_3 h^0$$

$$a_2^{\circ} = 15. a_6 h^4 + 10. a_5 h^3 + 6. a_4 h^2 + 3. a_3 h^1 + 1. a_2 h^0$$

$$a_1^{\circ} = 06. a_6 h^5 + 05. a_5 h^4 + 4. a_4 h^3 + 3. a_3 h^2 + 2. a_2 h^1 + 1. a_1 h^0$$

$$a_0^{\circ} = 01. a_6 h^6 + 01. a_5 h^5 + 1. a_4 h^4 + 1. a_3 h^3 + 1. a_2 h^2 + 1. a_1 h^1 + 1. a_0 h^0$$

12. Formal polynomial offset equation.

Because the offset variation of a polynomial sequence keeps the symmetry point with the coordinate x_{sp} constant and only y_{sp} is the one who varies in integer values, then we can generalize the offset formula to any polynomial of degree d as being:

$$offset = f = roundz[y_{sp}] = roundz\left[-\frac{a_{d-1}}{d \cdot a_d}\right] = round\left[-\frac{a_{d-1}}{d \cdot a_d} - infinitesimal\right]$$

We can say:

$$offset = f = round\left[-\frac{a_{d-1}}{d \cdot a_d} - \varepsilon\right] = round\left[f - \frac{a_{d-1}^o}{d \cdot a_d^o} - \varepsilon\right]$$

13. Formal definition of the simplest polynomial equation.

Remembering that our standard polynomial equation is $x = Yd[y] = a_d y^d + a_{d-1} y^{d-1} + \dots + a_4 y^4 + a_3 y^3 + a_2 y^2 + b y + c$, so let's find the simplest polynomial equation of all.

13.1. The Two directions of a Sequence.

Each polynomial sequence has only two directions. That is why all polynomial sequences have two recurrence equations <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8434818>.

One way we look at this is that given the polynomial equation $x = Yd[y] = a_d y^d + a_{d-1} y^{d-1} + \dots + a_4 y^4 + a_3 y^3 + a_2 y^2 + b y + c$, then $x = Yd[y] = a_d y^d - a_{d-1} y^{d-1} + \dots + a_4 y^4 + a_3 y^3 + a_2 y^2 + b y + c$ is its inverse sequence.

Whenever we invert the sign of the second highest coefficient, we change the offset of a sequence.

In symmetrical sequences, this phenomenon is more difficult to see. It is most evident in asymmetrical sequences. In all cases, we will consider the arrangement of its elements in both directions to be the same sequence.

In each of the two directions, when the index has its infinite absolute value, the generated element will also have an infinite value. If the polynomial is an even function, the sign of the two elements of infinite values is equal. If the polynomial is an odd function, the sign of the two elements of infinite values is opposite.

If $a_d > 0$ and $Y[y]$ is an even function, for $y \rightarrow \infty$, $Y[\pm y] \rightarrow \infty$.

If $a_d > 0$ and $Y[y]$ is an odd function, for $y \rightarrow \infty$, $Y[y] \rightarrow \infty$ and $Y[-y] \rightarrow -\infty$.

If $a_d < 0$ and $Y[y]$ is an even function, for $y \rightarrow \infty$, $Y[\pm y] \rightarrow -\infty$.

If $a_d < 0$ and $Y[y]$ is an odd function, for $y \rightarrow \infty$, $Y[y] \rightarrow -\infty$ and $Y[-y] \rightarrow \infty$.

13.2. The Two directions, symmetry point and offset.

But in all cases, the symmetry point is always located in the finite region where the absolute values of the elements of the polynomial sequence are the smallest possible. That is, from the symmetry point in some finite index we will find one or more equal elements that have the lowest value and the lowest absolute value. Sometimes they are the same element.

In any polynomial sequence we can only see a finite number of its infinite elements. It is precisely in this finite region visible to us that the symmetry point is located.

Also, at whatever the offset of the polynomial sequence, i.e., whatever the Taylor shift of the integer value of the polynomial curve is, the view that the symmetry point has with respect to all points of the polynomial curve is always the same. The offset varies, but the view of the symmetry point is always static and never changes.

13.3. The Signal Change

The last missing analysis is when we change the sign simultaneously in all the coefficients of the polynomial equation.

Just as the properties of integers do not change with the change of sign, we will also consider them to be the same polynomial sequence when we change the sign of all its elements:

$$Y[y] \leftrightarrow -Y[y]$$

13.4. The simplest polynomial equation of all.

Let's define the simplest polynomial equation of all as the one that:

- Own $a_d > 0$. That is to say, for $y > 0$ then $Y[y] \rightarrow \infty$ for odd and even function.
- Have the highest possible $a_{d-1} \leq 0$.

This last requirement is equivalent to:

$$0 \leq -\frac{a_{d-1}}{d \cdot a_d} \leq 0.5$$

14. Symmetry and asymmetry detection.

Because we have proven the existence of a symmetry point in any polynomial sequence, let us admit as a rule that every mathematical sequence has a symmetry point (sp) or point of symmetry or point of reference.

Therefore, we will always analyze the symmetry or asymmetry of any sequence using the symmetry point as our reference.

Following this principle, the view of the sequence elements through the symmetry point does not change with the offset. That is, to see all the sequence of elements of any sequence, we will always see from the symmetry point as our reference.

Every numerical sequence always has two recurrence equations, one for each direction.

Because of these facts, there are only three possibilities to check:

14.1.SUB-type polynomial.

If the symmetry point is one of the elements of the sequence, then it is a symmetric sequence of SUB-type.

The name SUB comes from SUBmarine, one position in the battleship game.

14.2.DES-type polynomial.

If the symmetry point is not an element of the sequence and it is equidistant from the two adjacent elements of the sequence, then it is also a symmetric sequence but of DES-type.

The name DES comes from DESTroyer, two positions in the battleship game.

14.3.ACC-type polynomial.

If the symmetry point is not an element of the sequence and is not equidistant from the two adjacent elements of the sequence, then the sequence is neither SUB nor DES. This is an asymmetric sequence, and we call it ACC-type.

The name ACC comes from AirCraft Carrier, three positions in the battleship game.

15. Bijection defines symmetry or asymmetry.

Let us assume that the reason for the symmetry or the asymmetry of any sequence is the result of the certainty or uncertainty of how to apply the bijection property.

This is independent of whether the sequence is finite or infinite.

Because the bijection property always applies to pairs of elements of a sequence (one-to-one correspondence), each of the pairs forms a duet.

15.1.Definition 1: the bijection function.

Definition 1: The bijection function will occur if and only if there exists a mathematical identity between the two elements of all the duets using the symmetry point as the reference.

- Consequence 1.1: The bijection function does not depend on the signs of the elements. The criterion to apply the bijection property (one-to-one correspondence) is

always solely the absolute value of the elements of the sequence. This fully applies to all polynomials of any degree.

- Consequence 1.2: The bijection function does not change when we offset a sequence.
- Consequence 1.3: The bijection function does not change when we analyze a sequence in ascending or descending order.
- Consequence 1.4: See that in this kind of definition, there is bijection even if the two elements of the duets of the sequences are not of equal absolute value.
 - For example, the sequence of the positive divisors of number 36 is a symmetric sequence of the SUB-type, and the sequence of the positive divisors of number 24 is also a symmetric sequence but of the DES-type.

15.2. Definition 2: symmetric sequences.

Definition 2: We will define any finite or infinite sequence of numbers as a symmetric sequence if and only if we can apply the bijection property (one-to-one correspondence) to all its elements precisely, without ambiguity.

- Consequence 2.1: When we apply the bijection function to all pairs of elements with the same absolute value or same mathematical property and it is impossible to leave out any element of the sequence, then this sequence is a DES-type.
 - Examples: (1) odd numbers, (2) quadratics in the form of (oblong numbers \pm an integer number), (3) positive and negative divisors of positive square numbers, (4) repetend of the inverse of some primes, etc.
- Consequence 2.2: When we apply the bijection function to all pairs of elements with the same absolute value or same mathematical property, and it is imperative to leave out of the bijection a unique single element of the sequence, then this sequence is a SUB-type.
 - Examples: (1) the number line, (2) the even numbers, (3) the quadratics in the form of (square numbers \pm an integer number), (4) the positive divisors of the positive square numbers*, etc.

* The number 1 is a square number with a single positive divisor and there is no duet of divisors formed. It is a case of a sequence of SUB-type of a single element.

In the context of symmetric sequences of integers, there are two kinds of certainties of application of the bijection function: DES-type and SUB-type.

15.3. Definition 3: asymmetric sequences.

Definition 3: We will define any finite or infinite sequence of numbers as an asymmetric sequence if and only if we can apply the bijection property (one-to-one correspondence) to all its elements precisely, with ambiguity.

That is, in an asymmetric polynomial sequence, we can apply the bijection property to all elements either leaving only a single element without bijection, or equally, it is possible to apply the bijection property to all elements without leaving any element out.

There is no absolute value equality between all elements of the duets, and there is the possibility of applying a mathematical identity between the elements in more than one form.

In the case of asymmetric sequences of integers, there is uncertainty about how to apply the bijection function. We name the asymmetric sequences ACC-type.

15.4. Example of an asymmetric sequence.

For an asymmetric example, let us take the sequence <https://oeis.org/A079588> or <https://oeis.org/A100147>.

See [C000446 https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/287517449571868/](https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/287517449571868/) for the sequence of data for the positive and negative indexes, as well as the sequence of its elements in the two possible directions.

See the summary here:

<https://oeis.org/A079588>
<https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/287517449571868/>
C000446

	Y_1 [y] = $8y^3 - 10y^2 + 3y$	Y_2 [y] = $-8y^3 + 10y^2 - 3y$	Y_3 [y] = $8y^3 + 10y^2 + 3y$	Y_4 [y] = $-8y^3 - 10y^2 - 3y$
f	0	0	0	0
Tally	1	2	3	4
a_4	0	0	0	0
a_3	8	-8	8	-8
a	-10	10	10	-10
b	3	-3	3	-3
c	0	0	0	0
-10	-9030	9030	-7030	7030
-9	-6669	6669	-5049	5049
-8	-4760	4760	-3480	3480
-7	-3255	3255	-2275	2275
-6	-2106	2106	-1386	1386
-5	-1265	1265	-765	765
-4	-684	684	-364	364
-3	-315	315	-135	135
-2	-110	110	-30	30
-1	-21	21	-1	1
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	-1	21	-21
2	30	-30	110	-110
3	135	-135	315	-315
4	364	-364	684	-684
5	765	-765	1265	-1265
6	1386	-1386	2106	-2106
7	2275	-2275	3255	-3255
8	3480	-3480	4760	-4760
9	5049	-5049	6669	-6669
10	7030	-7030	9030	-9030

Figure 6. C000446 Table study of the sequence A079588 or A100147 $x = 8y^3 - 10y^2 + 3y$.

For each equation of the same cubic sequence, we have a shift of the symmetry point as follows:

$$Y_1[y] = 8y^3 - 10y^2 + 3y \quad \text{sequence } \{\dots, -315, -110, -21, 0, 1, 30, 135, \dots\}.$$

$$y_{sp1} = -\frac{a}{3a_3} = -\frac{-10}{3 * 8} = \frac{5}{12} = 0.41\bar{6}$$

$$x_{sp} = 8\left(\frac{5}{12}\right)^3 - 10\left(\frac{5}{12}\right)^2 + 3\left(\frac{5}{12}\right) = \frac{5}{54} = 0.09\overline{25}$$

$$Y_2[y] = -8y^3 + 10y^2 - 3y \quad \text{sequence } \{\dots, 315, 110, 21, 0, -1, -30, -135, \dots\}.$$

$$y_{sp} = -\frac{a}{3a_3} = -\frac{10}{3 * (-8)} = \frac{5}{12} = 0.41\bar{6}$$

$$x_{sp2} = -8\left(\frac{5}{12}\right)^3 + 10\left(\frac{5}{12}\right)^2 - 3\left(\frac{5}{12}\right) = -\frac{5}{54} = -0.09\overline{25}$$

$$Y_3[y] = 8y^3 + 10y^2 + 3y \quad \text{sequence } \{\dots, -135, -30, -1, 0, 21, 110, 315, \dots\}.$$

$$y_{sp} = -\frac{a}{3a_3} = -\frac{10}{3 * 8} = -\frac{5}{12} = -0.41\bar{6}$$

$$x_{sp3} = 8\left(\frac{-5}{12}\right)^3 + 10\left(\frac{-5}{12}\right)^2 + 3\left(\frac{-5}{12}\right) = -\frac{5}{54} = -0.09\overline{25}$$

$$Y_4[y] = -8y^3 - 10y^2 - 3y \quad \text{sequence } \{\dots, 135, 30, 1, 0, -21, -110, -315, \dots\}.$$

$$y_{sp} = -\frac{a}{3a_3} = -\frac{-10}{3 * (-8)} = -\frac{5}{12} = -0.41\bar{6}$$

$$x_{sp} = -8\left(\frac{-5}{12}\right)^3 - 10\left(\frac{-5}{12}\right)^2 - 3\left(\frac{-5}{12}\right) = \frac{5}{54} = 0.09\overline{25}$$

Figure 7. C000446 Curves study of the sequence A079588 or A100147 $x = 8y^3 - 10y^2 + 3y$. The brown curves are reversed directions from the green curves. The dashed curves are the negative values of the non-dashed curves.

The criterion for applying the bijection function to the four sequence possibilities must be the same.

That is, because of definition 1 above, the criterion for applying the bijection function between pairs of elements cannot change when we see a sequence in one direction or the other or change the signal.

In each of these four sequences, no element has an absolute value repeated. That is, among the positive and negative elements, zero does not equally divide the two sides of the sequences.

This is the origin of asymmetry and why we must define the symmetry point as we did above.

First, let us use element 0 in the application of the bijection function. We have two alternatives to create the duets:

$$\{0; -21\}, \{1; -110\}, \{30; -315\}, \dots$$

or else,

$$\{0; -1\}, \{21; -30\}, \{110; -135\}, \dots$$

In either case, absolutely all elements of the sequences would correspond one-to-one. We call this bijection DES-type.

Therefore, it is a valid possibility.

However, we could push a little further and think that we can leave only the element 0 out of the bijection. In this case, we would have the following duets:

$$\{1; -21), \{30; -110\}, \{135; -315\}, \dots$$

or else,

$$\{-1; 21), \{-30; 110\}, \{-135; 315\}, \dots$$

Because only one single element (in this case, element 0) is out of the bijection, this bijection is a SUB-type.

In this case, we can only think about the absolute values of the elements; then, we would say that in this last SUB-type case, we have only a single possibility of bijection.

Finally, because of definition 3 above in this sequence, we can have the bijection function applied between its elements in the two ways: DES or SUB.

Because we do not know if we use DES or SUB, this is an asymmetric sequence, and there is an ambiguity or an uncertainty in the application of the bijection function.

Therefore, we classify it as an asymmetric sequence ACC-type.

16. Symmetric sequences.

We also define a symmetric sequence as all the sequences that satisfy symmetric relations with respect to taking additive or multiplicative inverses.

The polynomial integer sequences that satisfy symmetry relations, with respect to taking additive inverses, are the even functions and odd functions at https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Even_and_odd_functions. They are symmetric sequences.

All symmetric polynomial integer sequences have an infinite number of duplicated elements. When we apply the bijection function, each pair of duplicated elements forms a duet.

The quadratics and hyperbolic sequences are conic sequences with intrinsic symmetry.

The symmetry point of all polynomial sequences of type SUB at offset $f = 0$ occurs at $y = 0$.

The symmetry point of all polynomial sequences of type DES at offset $f = 0$ occurs at $y = \frac{1}{2}$.

The symmetry point of all polynomial sequences of type ACC at offset $f = 0$ occurs at $0 < |y| < \frac{1}{2}$.

Whenever the symmetry point of a polynomial is over the lines $y = 0$ or $y = \frac{1}{2}$, the sequence is symmetric. This is because in these cases, the symmetry line of the polynomial curve passes through the symmetry point.

Because in polynomial sequences $x = Y[y]$ of degree $d > 2$, the equality $Y[y] = \pm Y[-y]$ or $Y[y + 1] = \pm Y[-y]$ may occur for $|y| \leq \left\lfloor \frac{d}{2} \right\rfloor$, and even then, the sequence is not symmetric, then in a general way, we must write referring to offset $f = 0$:

- The SUB-type polynomials are in the form of $Y_{f=0} \left[y + \left\lfloor \frac{d}{2} \right\rfloor \right] = \pm Y_{f=0} \left[-y - \left\lfloor \frac{d}{2} \right\rfloor \right]$. And,
- The DES-type polynomials are in the form of $Y_{f=0} \left[y + \left\lfloor \frac{d}{2} \right\rfloor + 1 \right] = \pm Y_{f=0} \left[-y - \left\lfloor \frac{d}{2} \right\rfloor \right]$.

If these equalities occur at offset $f = 0$ for any $|y| \geq \left\lfloor \frac{d}{2} \right\rfloor$, then the polynomial sequence is symmetric of type SUB or DES. In other words, for any $|y| \geq \left\lfloor \frac{d}{2} \right\rfloor$, all symmetric polynomial integer sequences in the form of $Y[y]_{@f=0}$ are in one of the two forms:

- SUB-type polynomial where $Y[y] = \pm Y[-y]$, or
- DES-type polynomial where $Y[y + 1] = \pm Y[-y]$ or $Y[-y - 1] = \pm Y[y]$.

Because of these properties, it is easier and more direct to analyze the symmetry when the polynomial equation is at offset $f = 0$.

Along this line of reasoning, we can classify a sequence of integers as being symmetric (or palindromic) if we can unambiguously apply the bijection property among all its elements.

Now, we can define the symmetry or asymmetry of a sequence as follows:

16.1. Definition of SUB-type of symmetric sequence.

If we can perform the bijection directly and unambiguously by finding the one-to-one correspondence among all its infinite duet elements except one single element without bijection, then the sequence is symmetric of SUB-type.

In this case, the symmetry point (sp) of the sequence is an element of the sequence.

Mathematically, we define the polynomial SUB-type symmetry in offset $f = 0$ by:

$$F[Y[y]] = \pm F[Y[-y]]$$

In this case, the symmetry point (sp) of the polynomial curve $x = Y[y]$ has the Y-coordinate in the XY plane $y_{sp} = \pm integer$.

If the polynomial curve has offset $f = 0$, then $y_{sp} = 0$.

16.2. Definition of DES-type of symmetric sequence.

If we can perform the bijection directly and unambiguously by finding the one-to-one correspondence among all its infinite duet elements without exception, then the sequence is symmetric of DES-type.

In this case, the symmetry point (sp) of the sequence is not an element of the sequence but lies equidistant in the middle between two adjacent elements of the sequence.

Mathematically, we define the polynomial DES-type of symmetry in offset $f = 0$ by:

$$F[Y[-y]] = \pm F[Y[y + 1]]$$

In this case, the symmetry point (sp) of the polynomial curve $x = Y[y]$ has the Y-coordinate in the XY plane $y_{sp} = \pm \frac{odd}{2}$.

If the polynomial curve has offset $f = 0$, then $y_{sp} = \frac{1}{2}$.

16.3. Definition of ACC-type asymmetry sequence.

If we cannot perform the bijection directly and unambiguously by finding the one-to-one correspondence among all its infinite elements, this means we do not know if we can leave or not one single element without bijection. Consequently, the sequence is asymmetric of ACC-type.

ACC-type sequences are all sequences that can be either DES-type or SUB-type sequences.

In this case, the symmetry point (sp) of the sequence is not an element of the sequence but does not lie equidistant between two adjacent elements of the sequence.

Mathematically, we define polynomial ACC-type symmetry in offset $f = 0$ by

$$F[Y[y]] \neq \pm F[Y[-y]]$$

And,

$$F[Y[-y]] \neq \pm F[Y[y + 1]]$$

In this case, the symmetry point (sp) of the polynomial curve $x = Y[y]$ has the Y-coordinate in the XY plane $y_{sp} \neq \pm integer$ and $y_{sp} \neq \pm \frac{odd}{2}$.

If the polynomial curve has offset $f = 0$, then $0 < y_{sp} < 0.5$ and in the reversal direction $-0.5 < y_{sp} < 0$.

17. Line of symmetry.

All polynomial integer sequences have one straight line of symmetry.

The straight line of symmetry of any polynomial curve passes over the symmetry point of the curve.

For any polynomial integer sequence in the form of $x = Y[y]$, the line of symmetry is $y = y_{sp}$.

In offset $f = 0$, the line of symmetry is the most equidistant line between the elements of the duets $\{Y[y]; Y[-y]\}$ or $\{Y[y + 1]; Y[-y]\}$.

17.1.SUB-line of symmetry.

The SUB-line of symmetry in offset $f = 0$ is the straight line equidistant between the elements of the duets $\{Y[y]; Y[-y]\}$. Then, $Y[y] = Y[-y]$.

17.2.DES-line of symmetry.

The DES line of symmetry in offset $f = 0$ is the straight line equidistant between the elements of the duets $\{Y[y + 1]; Y[-y]\}$. Then, $Y[y + 1] = Y[-y]$

17.3.ACC-line of symmetry.

The ACC line of symmetry in offset $f = 0$ is the straight line most equidistant between duets $\{Y[y]; Y[-y]\}$ and $\{Y[y + 1]; Y[-y]\}$.

18. Pair of polynomial integer elements.

In the same way that all divisors of an integer form pairs of complementary divisors among themselves, the symmetry point of polynomial curves allows pairs of elements of polynomial sequences to be created.

When we apply the bijection function to a polynomial sequence of integers, we always create pairs of polynomial integer elements. They are the duets that result from the one-to-one correspondence.

18.1.SUB-pair of polynomial integer elements.

We define a pair of polynomial integer elements from a SUB-type polynomial sequence in any offset, any duet in the form of $\{Y[y_{sp} + m]; Y[y_{sp} - m]\}$, for $m = integer$.

We will name a SUB-duet or a SUB-pair of polynomial integer duplicated elements any pair $\{Y[y_{sp} + m]; \pm Y[y_{sp} - m]\}$ when $Y[y_{sp} + m] = \pm Y[y_{sp} - m]$.

18.2.DES-pair of polynomial integer elements.

We define a pair of polynomial integer elements from a DES-type polynomial sequence in any offset, any duet in the form of $\{Y[y_{sp} + m + 0.5]; Y[y_{sp} - m - 0.5]\}$, for $m = integer$.

We will name a DES-duet or a DES-pair of polynomial integer duplicated elements any pair $\{Y[y_{sp} + m + 0.5]; \pm Y[y_{sp} - m - 0.5]\}$ when $Y[y_{sp} + m + 0.5] = \pm Y[y_{sp} - m - 0.5]$.

18.3. ACC-pair of polynomial integer elements.

We define a pair of polynomial integer elements from an ACC-type polynomial sequence in any offset, any duet in the form of $\{Y[y_{sp} + m + r]; Y[y_{sp} - m - (1 - r)]\}$, for $m = \text{integer}, 0 < r < 1, r \neq \frac{1}{2}$.

There is no unique ACC-duets set because there is uncertainty about how to implement the one-to-one correspondence. Only SUB or DES symmetric polynomial integer sequences have a unique set of pairs of duplicated polynomial integer elements.

19. Central pair of polynomial integer elements.

The idea of classifying the central pair of elements in any polynomial arises because of the existence of the central pair of complementary divisors such that $d_{c2} \geq \pm\sqrt{|x|} \geq d_{c1}$, and $x = d_{c1} * d_{c2}$.

For positive divisors, d_{c1} is the sequence <https://oeis.org/A033676> and d_{c2} is the sequence <https://oeis.org/A033677>.

All symmetric polynomial integer sequences have a central pair of duplicated polynomial integer elements. The central pair of duplicated polynomial integer elements does not change with the offset.

19.1. The SUB-central pair of duplicated elements.

We define the SUB central pair of duplicated elements as the pair $\{Y[y_{sp} + 1]; \pm Y[y_{sp} - 1]\}$ when $Y[y_{sp} + 1] = \pm Y[y_{sp} - 1] = \text{integer}$.

They are the 2 closest elements of the symmetry point of the polynomial.

Consequently, $Y[y_{sp} + m] = \pm Y[y_{sp} - m]$ for any $m = \text{integer}, y_{sp} = \text{integer}$ and $x_{sp} = Y[y_{sp}] = \text{integer}$ is an element of the sequence.

19.2. The DES-central pair of duplicated elements.

We will define the DES central pair of duplicated elements as the pair $\{Y[y_{sp} + 0.5]; \pm Y[y_{sp} - 0.5]\}$ when $Y[y_{sp} + 0.5] = \pm Y[y_{sp} - 0.5] = \text{integer}$.

They are the 2 closest elements of the symmetry point of the polynomial.

Consequently, $Y[y_{sp} + 0.5 + m] = \pm Y[y_{sp} - 0.5 - m]$ for any $m = \text{integer}, y_{sp} = \frac{\text{odd}}{2}$ and $x_{sp} = Y[y_{sp}] \neq \text{integer}$ is not an element of the sequence.

19.3. The ACC-central pair of elements.

We define the ACC central pair of duplicated elements as the pair $(Y[y_{sp} + r]; \pm Y[y_{sp} - (1 - r)])$, both integer numbers when $Y[y_{sp} + r] \neq \pm Y[y_{sp} - (1 - r)]$ for $0 < r < 1$, and $r \neq \frac{1}{2}$.

They are the 2 closest elements of the symmetry point of the polynomial.

Consequently, $y_{sp} \neq \frac{odd}{2}$ and $y_{sp} \neq integer$ and $x_{sp} = Y[y_{sp}] \neq integer$ are not elements of the sequence.

They may have a finite number of pairs of duplicated polynomial integer elements. Necessarily, they have an infinite number of pairs of nonduplicated polynomial integer elements.

For example, $Y6[y] = \{2,0,0,0,0,1\}$. The central pair of duplicated elements is $\{0,0\}$, but it is an asymmetric sequence.

20. Example of the geometry in an ACC-quadratic manner.

See the example for the asymmetric polynomial integer sequence $x = Y[y] = 2y^2 - y$ green parabola curve in the XY-plane:

The integer sequence data $x = Y[y] = 2y^2 - y$ for $-10 \leq y \leq 10$ are $\{210, 171, 136, 105, 78, 55, 36, 21, 10, 3, 0, 1, 6, 15, 28, 45, 66, 91, 120, 153, 190\}$.

The closest element to sp is $x = 0$. This is a root of the polynomial equation at the XY-plane coordinate $(0,0)$. The distance between them is $l = \sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{1}{8}\right)^2} = \frac{\sqrt{5}}{8} = 0.2795\dots$

For a <https://www.mersenneforum.org/showpost.php?p=632904&postcount=42> complementary study, the roots of $2y^2 - y - \frac{\sqrt{5}}{8} = 0$ are $\frac{1 \pm \sqrt{2\Phi}}{4} = \{0.6997268 \dots, -0.1997268 \dots\}$, $sum = 0.5$ and $product = \frac{1-2\Phi}{16} = \frac{-\sqrt{5}}{16} = -0,139754 \dots$

Because at index $y = 1$ we have the second closest element $x = 1$ to SP, then $x = Y[y] = 2y^2 - y$ is the equation at offset $f = 0$.

If we had used the equation $x = Y[y] = 2y^2 + y$, which is represented in a dashed line in the figure above, then for the index $y = 1$ we would have the third closest element $x = 3$ to the SP. This is because the integer sequence data for $x = Y[y] = 2y^2 - y$ for $-10 \leq y \leq 10$ is $\{190, 153, 120, 91, 66, 45, 28, 15, 6, 1, 0, 3, 10, 21, 36, 55, 78, 105, 136, 171, 210\}$. This is the offset $f = -1$.

In both cases, the element closest to SP is element 0.

Triangles \widehat{ABC} and \widehat{CDE} are congruent and isosceles nonrectangular. They are based on the X-axis. If the polynomial sequence were SUB-type $x = Y[y] = 2y^2$ or DES-type $x = Y[y] = 2y^2 - 2y$ symmetric, then these triangles would be rectangles.

Because of asymmetry, triangles based on the line of symmetry are also isosceles equivalent but never congruent. Triangle $SP1.\widehat{B}.SP2$ is equivalent to triangle $SP2.\widehat{D}.SP3$.

For our reference, see this integer sequence in both directions in the offset range $-3 \leq f \leq 3$:

Tally	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
x_sp	-0.125	-0.125	-0.125	-0.125	-0.125	-0.125	-0.125
y_sp	-2.75	-1.75	-0.75	0.25	1.25	2.25	3.25
f	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3
type	ACC						
a	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
b	11	7	3	-1	-5	-9	-13
c	15	6	1	0	3	10	21
20	1035	946	861	780	703	630	561
19	946	861	780	703	630	561	496
18	861	780	703	630	561	496	435
17	780	703	630	561	496	435	378
16	703	630	561	496	435	378	325
15	630	561	496	435	378	325	276
14	561	496	435	378	325	276	231
13	496	435	378	325	276	231	190
12	435	378	325	276	231	190	153
11	378	325	276	231	190	153	120
10	325	276	231	190	153	120	91
9	276	231	190	153	120	91	66
8	231	190	153	120	91	66	45
7	190	153	120	91	66	45	28
6	153	120	91	66	45	28	15
5	120	91	66	45	28	15	6
4	91	66	45	28	15	6	1
3	66	45	28	15	6	1	0
2	45	28	15	6	1	0	3
1	28	15	6	1	0	3	10
0	15	6	1	0	3	10	21
-1	6	1	0	3	10	21	36
-2	1	0	3	10	21	36	55
-3	0	3	10	21	36	55	78
-4	3	10	21	36	55	78	105
-5	10	21	36	55	78	105	136
-6	21	36	55	78	105	136	171
-7	36	55	78	105	136	171	210
-8	55	78	105	136	171	210	253
-9	78	105	136	171	210	253	300
-10	105	136	171	210	253	300	351
-11	136	171	210	253	300	351	406
-12	171	210	253	300	351	406	465
-13	210	253	300	351	406	465	528
-14	253	300	351	406	465	528	595
-15	300	351	406	465	528	595	666
-16	351	406	465	528	595	666	741
-17	406	465	528	595	666	741	820
-18	465	528	595	666	741	820	903
-19	528	595	666	741	820	903	990
-20	595	666	741	820	903	990	1081

Tally	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
x_sp	-0.125	-0.125	-0.125	-0.125	-0.125	-0.125	-0.125
y_sp	-3.25	-2.25	-1.25	-0.25	0.75	1.75	2.75
f	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3
type	ACC						
a	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
b	13	9	5	1	-3	-7	-11
c	21	10	3	0	1	6	15
20	1081	990	903	820	741	666	595
19	990	903	820	741	666	595	528
18	903	820	741	666	595	528	465
17	820	741	666	595	528	465	406
16	741	666	595	528	465	406	351
15	666	595	528	465	406	351	300
14	595	528	465	406	351	300	253
13	528	465	406	351	300	253	210
12	465	406	351	300	253	210	171
11	406	351	300	253	210	171	136
10	351	300	253	210	171	136	105
9	300	253	210	171	136	105	78
8	253	210	171	136	105	78	55
7	210	171	136	105	78	55	36
6	171	136	105	78	55	36	21
5	136	105	78	55	36	21	10
4	105	78	55	36	21	10	3
3	78	55	36	21	10	3	0
2	55	36	21	10	3	0	1
1	36	21	10	3	0	1	6
0	21	10	3	0	1	6	15
-1	10	3	0	1	6	15	28
-2	3	0	1	6	15	28	45
-3	0	1	6	15	28	45	66
-4	1	6	15	28	45	66	91
-5	6	15	28	45	66	91	120
-6	15	28	45	66	91	120	153
-7	28	45	66	91	120	153	190
-8	45	66	91	120	153	190	231
-9	66	91	120	153	190	231	276
-10	91	120	153	190	231	276	325
-11	120	153	190	231	276	325	378
-12	153	190	231	276	325	378	435
-13	190	231	276	325	378	435	496
-14	231	276	325	378	435	496	561
-15	276	325	378	435	496	561	630
-16	325	378	435	496	561	630	703
-17	378	435	496	561	630	703	780
-18	435	496	561	630	703	780	861
-19	496	561	630	703	780	861	946
-20	561	630	703	780	861	946	1035

From all these possible offset equations, the two simplest ones are $x = Y[y] = 2y^2 \pm y$.

Note that both sequences have offset $f = 0$. We have two sequences with offset $f = 0$ because the sequence is asymmetric.

Because of the Y-coordinate of the symmetry points, these two equations have a Taylor shift difference of $|\Delta h| = \frac{1}{2}$.

Applying a Taylor shift of $h = \frac{1}{2}$ in $x = Y[y] = 2y^2 - y$, we obtain $x = Y[y + h] = 2y^2 + y$.

Obviously, applying a Taylor shift of $h = -\frac{1}{2}$ to $x = Y[y] = 2y^2 + y$, we obtain $x = Y[y + h] = 2y^2 - y$.

In both cases, the Taylor shift and fit is equal to the Taylor shift. That is, there is no need for compensation to perform the noninteger Taylor shift and produce a polynomial sequence of integers again.

All these equations generate only a single sequence. It is just a matter of the direction of the index or the direction of the recurrence equation. Recall that the recurrence equation comes from Pascal's triangle, which is palindromic (symmetric) in its rows.

This shows us that it makes no sense to attribute two different classifications to each equation.

Assigning a different classification just because we reversed the direction of a sequence is equivalent to assigning a different classification just because we swapped the sign of all elements in the sequence.

In the same line of reasoning, because any polynomial of degree d needs only a finite number $(d + 1)$ of elements to produce the equation and the polynomial sequence, in this case, we can say that this sequence is:

$$x = Y[y] = \{3,0,1\}$$

This is an example where a sequence with a finite number of elements completely identifies a polynomial sequence with an infinite number of elements.

This finite data set, always in offset $f = 0$, is sufficient to express both <https://oeis.org/A000384> and <https://oeis.org/A014105>.

21. Summary for quadratics.

See the classification of the quadratic sequences.

Classification of quadratic sequences in the form of $x=Y[y]=ay^2+by+c$			
Type	SUB (submarine)	ACC (aircraft carrier)	DES (destroyer)
Characteristic I	Only one element is not duplicated.	No element is duplicated.	All elements are duplicated.
Characteristic II	Quadratics with infinitely many pairs of duplicated integer elements.	Quadratics with a finite number or no pair of duplicated integer element.	Quadratics with infinitely many pairs of duplicated integer elements.
Characteristic III	Parabolas with the symmetry point over one element with both XY-coordinates integer.	Parabolas with the symmetry point with no XY-coordinates integer nor odd/2.	Parabolas with the symmetry point equidistant from the 2 adjacent elements.
Infinite number of symmetric and duplicated elements	Yes	No	Yes
Symmetry point over one element	Yes	No	No
Symmetry axis over one element	Yes	No	No
Pairs of duplicated elements	Yes	No	Yes
Symmetry point equidistant from the duplicated elements	Yes	No	Yes
2nd degree coefficients for offset zero ($f=0$)	$ a > b = 0$	$ a \neq b > 0$	$ a = b \neq 0$
$y_{sp} = -b/2a$	$y_{sp} = \text{integer}$	$y_{sp} \neq \text{odd}/2$, and $y_{sp} \neq \text{integer}$	$y_{sp} = \text{odd}/2$
$x_{sp} = Y[y_{sp}] = -(b^2-4ac)/4a$	$x_{sp} = c = \text{integer}$	$x_{sp} = c - b^2/4a \neq \text{integer}$	$x_{sp} = c - a/4 \neq \text{integer}$
Closest element(s) to the symmetry point	$Y[y_{sp}]$	Not $Y[y_{sp}]$ neither $Y[y_{sp} \pm 0.5]$	$Y[y_{sp} \pm 0.5]$
The symmetry from symmetry point	$Y[y_{sp}+n] = Y[y_{sp}-n]$	no symmetry	$Y[y_{sp}+0.5+n] = Y[y_{sp}-0.5-n]$
The triangle formed by the symmetry point and the closest pair of integer elements	Isosceles	never Isosceles	Isosceles
Offset (f) equation	$f = \text{roundz}[y_{sp}] = \text{roundz}[-b/2a]$		
Mouth aperture of the parabola	For $a>0$, $x=Y[y]$ is a C-type parabola curve.		
	For $a<0$, $x=Y[y]$ is a D-type parabola curve.		

Figure 8. [C001108](#) Quadratics classification summary.

22. Summary for any polynomial.

See the classification for any polynomial sequence.

Classification of any polynomial sequence in the form of $x=Y[y]$			
Type	SUB (submarine)	ACC (aircraft carrier)	DES (destroyer)
Characteristic I	Only one element is not duplicated.	Zero or maximum a finite number of elements are duplicated.	All elements are duplicated.
Characteristic II	Infinite number of pairs of duplicated elements.	An infinite number of elements non-duplicated.	Infinite number of pairs of duplicated elements.
Characteristic III	Polynomial curve with the symmetry point over one element with both XY-coordinates integer.	Polynomial curve with the symmetry point with no XY-coordinates integer nor odd/2.	Polynomial curve with the symmetry point equidistant from the 2 adjacent elements.
Infinite number of symmetric and duplicated elements	Yes	No	Yes
Symmetry point over one element	Yes	No	No
Symmetry axis over one element	Yes	No	No
Pairs of duplicated elements	Yes	No	Yes
Symmetry point equidistant from the duplicated elements	Yes	No	Yes
Closest element(s) to the symmetry point	$Y[y_{sp}]$	Not $Y[y_{sp}]$ neither $Y[y_{sp}\pm 0.5]$	$Y[y_{sp}\pm 0.5]$
The symmetry from symmetry point	$Y[y_{sp}+n] = Y[y_{sp}-n]$	$Y[y_{sp}+n] \neq Y[y_{sp}-n]$, and $Y[y_{sp}+0.5+n] \neq Y[y_{sp}-0.5-n]$	$Y[y_{sp}+0.5+n] = Y[y_{sp}-0.5-n]$
The triangle formed by the symmetry point and the closest pair of integer elements	Isosceles	never Isosceles	Isosceles
Offset (f) equation	$f = \text{roundz}[y_{sp}]$		

Figure 9. [C001108](#) Polynomial classification summary.

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Conflicts of Interest.

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

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